

Inky Night: A Nineteenth-Century Urban Legend

Introduction to Inky Night

Fourteenth August 2024 Chris Woodyard discovered a nineteenth-century belief legend that I've called here 'Inky Night' (I was tempted by 'Ink-credible Night' but was worried about searchability). Brian Chapman and Bonny Taylor-Blake then came up with a score of other examples, to which I added some of my own: I've initialled the examples below with BC, BTB, CW, and SY according to whom discovered them. They are in chronological order.

There are many variants of the tale, but perhaps the most successful have a man taken ill in the night. His wife rubs some 'liniment' on whatever part of his body hurts. In the morning the couple discover that she had actually rubbed ink. In some versions there is an initial misinterpretation at dawn: the husband is thought to be a coloured man (in the versions here the ink users are white), or the subject is thought to be dangerously ill.

My suspicion is that there is also here a sexual tale that was unprintable in the Victorian period. A man and woman break from their love-making. The man leaves the room and the woman takes the opportunity to put on perfume. But she accidentally uses an ink bottle... When the man returns with a light, he runs screaming on seeing his paramour transformed. An alleged 16C tale of this sort is detailed in 'Cut and Come Again' (1883). I've not been able to find the original. It may not exist...

Search terms used by myself included: 'bottle', 'ink', 'night', 'liniment', 'morning', 'rheumatism', 'light', 'mistake', 'dark' and 'bed'. I also experimented with 'bottle of ink', 'ink bottle', 'mistaken for', 'holy water'.

I used Google Lens to 'rip' the text. This is a very quick method. But I have not taken the time to go through and check the quality of the OCD beyond the basics.

I've also included five appendices: The Holy Water Joke; Thieves Drink Ink; Death by Ink; The Blotting Paper Joke; and Ink Miscellany. These have not been properly referenced or 'ripped' for text. There is a final bibliography and the different versions are set out in a rubric overleaf.

There will be many more examples out there and anyone who stumbles on an Inky Night is invited to send it to me Simon Young at simonyoungflATgmailDOTcom so the file can be updated. I hope to include Inky Night in the follow up volume to my *Nail in the Skull and other Victorian Urban Legends*. I'm also intrigued by this sentence: 'Sounds like the guy I heard about who grabbed a can of spray paint thinking it was deodorant' ('The August issue of...' 1973)! Languages other than English welcomed.

Thanks to Bonny Taylor-Blake, Brian Chapman and Chris Woodyard.

Simon Young 15 Aug 2024

Second edition, 16 Aug 2024. A few more stories have been added, and a couple more appendices. The sixteenth-century legend seems to be Bandello, *novella* 48. I've also

come across a reference to a similar legend in Rainer Wehse, *Schwanklied und Flugblatt in Grossbritannien* (1979), §502 in reference to a British broadside or chapbook. If anyone has a copy... I cannot easily get my hands on this volume. Note, too, Uther 1441A, The Inked Girl. 'A young woman is brought to an old man to spend the night with him. During the night she smears herself with black ink. The next morning, when the man sees the black face beside him, he thinks he has slept with the devil'. Found largely in Russia and Finland? This seems to have been a deliberate choice on the part of the girl, not an accident as here.

Simon Young 13 Jan 2025

The seventeenth century work in Wehse (thank you Rainer!) is *A New delightful Ballad. Called, / Debauchery Scared: / OR, THE / Beggar wench turn'd into a Devil, / Together with the Pollicy of Bumpkin; / Giving a peasant Account of Commical Passages between a Country Gentle / man, and a London Beggar-wench* (London: Printed for J. Bissel at the Bible and Harp, ND [1685-1688]. Now appendix H. Most importantly, Peter Burger supplied a remarkable series of Dutch cases. I've put these as appendix I. Of course, eventually the different language accounts would need to be integrated. But for now let's be provincial... Filip Graliński also contributed a Polish example in Appendix K.

Problem	Confusion	Reason	Application	Guilt	Interpretation
1859 fainting	brandy	panic	swallow	servant	N/A
1867 beautifying	perfume	dark	apply	self	N/A
1870 mosquitoes	coal oil	dark	apply	self	N/A
1872 toothache	liniment	dark	apply	self	illness
1873 cholera	cholera medicine	dark	apply	self	N/A
1874 beautifying	perfume	dark	apply	self	N/A
1875 washing	stove blacking	dark	apply	self	N/A
1879 mosquitoes	camphor	dark	apply	wife	racial
1881 beautifying	hair tonic	dark	apply	self	N/A
1883 rheumatism	liniment	dark	apply	servant	illness
1892 rheumatism	liniment	dark	apply	wife	N/A
1892 rheumatism	liniment	dark	apply	wife	N/A
1892 lightning	holy water	dark	apply	wife	racial
1895 rheumatism	liniment	dark	apply	wife	N/A
1895 fainting	camphor	panic	apply	judge	N/A
1896 beautifying	perfume	?	apply	self	insane
1899 lightning	holy water	dark	apply	sister	N/A
1899 heart	liniment	dark	apply	self	N/A
1901 lightning	holy water	dark	apply	wife	N/A
1902 drunk	brandy	dark	swallow	self	murder
1902 toothache	brandy	dark	apply	self	N/A
1902 toothache	tincture	dark	swallow	wife?	N/A
1908 beautifying	tooth powder	dark	apply	self	racial?
1912 beautifying	water	?	apply	child	N/A
1921 ankle pain	liniment	dark	apply	self	N/A
1938 croup	medicine	dark	apply	stand in for mother	N/A
1957 chest	vapo-rub	dark	apply	self	N/A
1973 cold	nose drops	dark	apply	wife	N/A
1978 beautifying	face lotion	dark	apply	self	N/A

1859: Parlor Theatricals

Enter SUSAN.

SUSAN. Here it is, sir. [Gives bottle to JOE.]

JOE. Now then, we'll soon have him right.

[JOE uncorks the bottle, MRS. FONDLEIGH and SUSAN look on, in breathless anxiety. JOE pours the contents of the bottle down FRED's throat.

FRED jumps up, and runs to foot of stage.

FRED. (coughing and spluttering.) Ugh! weugh! pish!

MRS. FONDLEIGH. Thank goodness! it has brought him to.

JOE. How do you feel now, Fred?

FRED. (aside to JOE.) What made you give me ink?

JOE (looks at bottle, then bursts into a laugh.) (Aside.) By Jove! she brought down the ink bottle in mistake for the brandy.

MRS. FONDLEIGH. My dear boy, are you better now?

FRED. Yes, thank you, aunt, but I feel very weak.

MRS. FONDLEIGH. What had he better do for weakness, Mr. Dashington?

JOE. Change of air, I should recommend, and the sooner the better.

MRS. FONDLEIGH. He shall have change of air. Fred., dear, there's some money. (Gives pocket-book.) You had better start as soon as possible.

FRED. Oh, aunt, this kindness!

JOE. Keep quiet, old fellow, you mustn't get excited, or I won't answer for the consequences.

Enter SUSAN.

SUSAN. Here it is, sir. [Gives bottle to JOE.]

[JOE uncorks the bottle, MRS. FONDLEIGH and SUSAN look on, in breathless anxiety.

JOE. Now then, we'll soon have him right.

JOE pours the contents of the bottle down FRED's throat. FRED jumps up, and runs to foot of stage, FRED. (coughing and spluttering.) Ugh! weugh! pish!

MRS. FONDLEIGH. Thank goodness! it has brought him to.

JOE. How do you feel now, Fred?

FRED. (aside to JOE.) What made you give me ink?

JOE (looks at bottle, then bursts into a laugh.) (Aside.) By Jove! she brought down the ink bottle in mistake for the brandy.

MRS. FONDLEIGH. My dear boy, are you better now?

FRED. Yes, thank you, aunt, but I feel very weak.

George Arnold, *Parlor Theatricals: Or, Winter Evenings' Entertainment* (New York: Dick and Fitzgerald, 1859), 97 [SY]

1869: A Quiet Corner

After the companion was gone, and while I was completing my ablutions, I could not help soliloquizing aloud to myself — “And so my fair correspondent was Mdlle. Jacottet, *alias* Boa Constrictor! *Vanitas vanitatum, et omnia vanitas!* Provided only that the melancholy fact does not get wind, I shall recover the shock,” and down I went to the dining-room. Most of the company were already at table, some few laggards like myself were taking their chairs. I went straight to my accustomed seat, and I was in the act of sitting down, when — (even now at the recollection my hair stands on end) — when an universal shout of laughter welcomed my appearance, and I found every eye riveted on me. My guilty conscience could suggest only one explanation for this extraordinary

Digitized by Google

AFTER THE TRAGEDY, THE FARCE. 189

reception. No doubt, my secret was already the sport of the public. But how? who could have told? Mdlle. Jacottet's companion had betrayed me and it. I felt myself growing all the colours of the rainbow, and drops of cold perspiration rose on my forehead. Had the floor beneath me opened and swallowed up my chair and me, I should have been thankful. This terrible suspense lasted only a few seconds, but they were seconds of exquisite agony.

Herr Konrad, rising from his place, purple with convulsive laughter, took me by the arm, and forcing me also to rise, led me in front of a mirror. No sooner did I catch sight of myself than I joined in the homeric hilarity shaking the very windows in the room. Impossible to do justice to the figure I was. All the lower part of my face, including the tip of my nose, was one mass of black. How had it happened? The explanation was this. I am an inveterate smoker, as the reader is aware, but I make it a point that nobody, especially my neighbours at table, above all if such were ladies, should suffer from this my habit; and so, besides washing before dinner, as all good Christians do, it is my custom to pour a little eau de cologne into the palm of my hand, and pass it over my moustache and chin. This operation I used to perform at Schranksteinbad almost in the dark, for the door of the cupboard in which I kept my eau de cologne opened against the window, of which the blinds, as a rule, were down. Now, the eau de cologne bottle was not the only one in the cupboard. There were several others, and in the number was a bottle of ink; and this, in my to-day's bewilderment, I had used instead of the eau de cologne, thus unwittingly qualifying myself for

190

A QUIET NOOK.

Othello's part. It took a good week to efface from my skin all trace of the ink.

The moral of my tale is so short, that I venture on giving it: Never trust to circumstantial evidence, however conclusive it may appear. Let jurymen reflect on this!

After the companion was gone, and while I was completing my ablutions, I could not help soliloquizing aloud to myself: 'And so my fair correspondent was Mdlle. Jacottet, alias Boa Constrictor! Vanitas vanitatum, et omnia vanitas! Provided only that the melancholy fact does not get wind, I shall recover the shock,' and down I went to the dining-room. Most of the company were already at table, some few laggards like myself were taking their chairs. I went straight to my accustomed seat, and I was in the act of sitting down, when -(even now at the recollection my hair stands on end) - when an universal shout of laughter welcomed my appearance, and I found every eye riveted on me. My guilty conscience could suggest only one explanation for this extraordinary [189] reception. No doubt, my secret was already the sport of the public. But how? who could have told? Mdlle. Jacottet's companion had betrayed me and it. I felt myself growing all the colours of the rainbow, and drops of cold perspiration rose on my forehead. Had the

floor beneath me opened and swallowed up my chair and me, I should have been thankful. This terrible suspense lasted only a few seconds, but they were seconds of exquisite agony. Herr Konrad, rising from his place, purple with convulsive laughter, took me by the arm, and forcing me also to rise, led me in front of a mirror. No sooner did I catch sight of myself than I joined in the homeric hilarity shaking the very windows in the room. Im- possible to do justice to the figure I was. All the lower part of my face, including the tip of my nose, was one mass of black. How had it happened? The explanation was this. I am an inveterate smoker, as the reader is aware, but I make it a point that nobody, especially my neighbours at table, above all if such were ladies, should suffer from this my habit; and so, besides washing before dinner, as all good Christians do, it is my custom to pour a little eau de cologne into the palm of my hand, and pass it over my moustache and chin. This operation I used to perform at Schranksteinbad almost in the dark, for the door of the cupboard in which I kept my eau de cologne opened against the window, of which the blinds, as a rule, were down. Now, the eau de cologne bottle was not the only one in the cupboard. There were several others, and in the number was a bottle of ink; and this, in my to-day's bewilderment, I had used instead of the eau de cologne, thus unwittingly qualifying myself for [190] Othello's part. It took a good week to efface from my skin all trace of the ink. The moral of my tale is so short, that I venture on giving it: Never trust to circumstantial evidence, how- ever conclusive it may appear. Let jurymen reflect on this!

Giovanni Ruffini, *A Quiet Nook in the Jura* (Edinburgh: Edmonston and Douglas, 1867) [SY]

1870: 'Current Notes'

A gentleman in Louisville smeared his face with coal oil to keep away mosquitoes. A few nights since, feeling that previous smearings were insufficient, he arose and repeated the dose. Next morning his wife awoke and bounded out of bed with a scream. He also jumped out and going to the looking glass, discovered that he had used ink instead of coal oil.

A gentleman in Louisville smeared his face with coal oil to keep away mosquitoes. A few nights since, feeling that previous smearings were insufficient, he arose and repeated the dose. Next morning his wife awoke and bounded out of bed with a scream. He also jumped out and going to the looking glass, discovered that he had used ink instead of coal oil.

'Current Notes', *Knoxville Weekly Chronicle* (3 Aug 1870), 7 [BTB]

1872: A Mt. Morris...

profitable investment.

A Mt. Morris girl who had the tooth ache, made a mistake in applying a remedy in the night, and got hold of a bottle of purple ink instead of liniment. The inside of her mouth, teeth, and blooming cheeks were found of a peculiar color in the morning, much to the alarm of the lady and her friends. They were relieved to find it only a mortifying mistake and not a mortifying face.

We saw, on Thursday, as indicative of a

A Mt. Morris girl who had the tooth ache, made a mistake in the applying a remedy in the night, and got hold of a bottle of purple ink instead of liniment. The inside of her mouth, teeth, and blooming cheeks were found of a peculiar color in the morning, much to the alarm of the lady and her friends. They were relieved to find it only a mortifying mistake and not a mortifying face.

'A Mt. Morris girl...', *Sterling Standard* (21 Nov 1872), 1 [BTB]

1873: A Cholera Incident

A CHOLERA INCIDENT.—[Princeton (Ky.) *Binner*.]—It is said of one of our townsmen, who was quite shaky in the knees during the cholera storm, that during one night he was taken with a "terrible griping," and desirous of "nipping the thing in the bud," and unwilling to lose a moment of time in so doing by lighting his lamp, reached out and clutched from a table standing close by his bottle of limpid cholera medicine, took a heavy draught, and rubbed the balance on the parts where the "griping" was raging. He immediately experienced great relief and fell into a sound slumber, praising the skill of his physician, and congratulating himself upon his forethought in providing himself with the aforesaid medicine. Imagine how he felt next morning when he discovered the fact that his cholera medicine bottle was still full, but his *ink bottle was empty*.

It is said of one of our townsmen, who was quite shaky in the knees during the cholera storm, that during one night he was taken with a ‘terrible griping,’ and desirous of ‘nipping the thing in the bud.’ and unwilling to lose a moment of time in so doing by lighting his lamp, reached out and clutched from a table standing close by his bottle of limpid cholera medicine, took a heavy draught, and rubbed the balance on the parts where the ‘griping’ was raging. He immediately experienced great relief and fell into a sound slumber, praising the skill of his physician, and congratulating himself upon his forethought in providing himself with the aforesaid medicine. Imagine how he felt next morning when he discovered the fact that his cholera medicine bottle was still full, but his ink bottle was empty.

‘A Cholera Incident’, *Richmond [VA] Dispatch* (4 Sep 1873) 4 [CW]

1874: What We...

g odor generally emanating from her favorite fo
d bottle. Upon her appearance in the parlor
r the young man snickered and laughed, she ea
ot blushed and was very much embarrassed, not w
n knowing what he was laughing at. She be
as took her handkerchief from her pocket to in
h hide her blushes and in doing so she discov- th
ot ered the cause of his laughter. She had E
— taken a bottle of ink instead of cologne. ho
os Her handkerchief was black, her beautiful
l. face was striped and her delicate hands as D
ol black as the ace of spaces. She gave vent pr
e to a shower of tears and at last accounts she do
t was rubbing and scrubbing to remove the th
t ink. She says she will never use perfumery m
e again without first testing her smelling or or
is gan. When nature has endowed you with so be
e much beauty, you should never use artificial sh
e means to render yourself still more beauti- ex
o ful.—The pedestrian fever has reached be
l this place. The

Upon her appearance in the parlor the young man snickered and laughed, she blushed and was very much embarrassed, not knowing what he was laughing at. She took her handkerchief from her pocket to hide her blushes and in doing so she discovered the cause of his laughter. She had taken a bottle of ink instead of cologne. Her handkerchief was black, her beautiful face was striped and her delicate hands as black as the ace of spaces. She gave vent to a shower of tears and at last accounts she was rubbing and scrubbing to remove the ink. She says she will never use perfumery again without first testing her smelling organ. When nature has endowed you with so much beauty, you should never use artificial means to render yourself still more beautiful.

‘What We heard [sic] and Saw within the Week’, *The Jeffersonian* (28 May 1874), 2 [BTB]

1875: A man...

A man recently took a bath in the dark. He managed well enough, only he got hold of a piece of stove blacking instead of soap – with marked results.

‘A man...’, *The St. Helena [CA] Star* (23 Sep 1875), 4 [CW]

1879: The Latest Yarn...

Portsmouth Evening News - Thursday 20 November 1879

< Page 3 of 4 >

Image © THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD. ALL RIGHTS RESERVED.

anatical religious opinions. God in his kingdom, but should go to heaven in their opinion. Justice was that it to all, provided that it did not conflict with political interests. He considered it an advantage, as he thought it would be in his hands than without their scribbled as another name for a word invented for the object is to gain advantages. In constructs and maintains as an example of policy. It is always before the eyes of the men. He is censured a major for the men. If a regiment was ordered it fifteen were allowed to dine with him. It acquitted itself well, the king in the royal presence. He knew to establish himself a very great success. His no means flattering, as he said, but declared that it was a reward and support them. It is them their pensions because they would in consequence and which affected them in their advised that all subjects

THE LATEST YARN FROM AMERICA.

An example of the danger of placing bottles which, from their form, may be mistaken for each other, in contiguity, is afforded by a touching story which comes to us from Green Bay, in Wisconsin. At this place reside the M'Ginnises, a pair noted among their neighbours for mutual affection and good conduct. M'Ginnis is a local carrier by trade, and he one day appeared at work in a sadly battered state. His general appearance, in fact, suggested that he had been engaged in a difficulty with a locomotive engine running at full speed, and that subsequently all the coal dust in the tender had been poured over him. Of course, little was said to him on the subject, as he showed a disposition of reticence by knocking down the first man who indelicately called public attention to him. As, upon Mrs. M'Ginnis appearing in public on the same day, it was found that her physiognomy had equally suffered, persons came to the conclusion that, unlikely as it appeared between so loving a couple, a family difficulty had arisen. It was not until some months later that Mr. M'Ginnis, in a diffusive moment, explained the cause of the appearances which had so puzzled and astonished his neighbours. Green Island, like most other parts of Wisconsin, is covered with masses of a large and

The Lord Chief Justice of opinion that they should have had not authority to present evidence he should have had only to take sufficient committal, and in his was quite right in rejecting Lush and Manisty and therefore, dismissed with

ELECTION

Mr. Eyre Lloyd of intimated his intention servative Home Rule Limerick county at election.

THE ACCIDENT

The sufferers where etc

appearances which had so puzzled and astonished his neighbour. Green Island, like most other parts of Wisconsin, is plagued with mosquitoes of a large and peculiarly vindictive kind. On the night in question the mosquito net at M'Ginnis's got out of order, and the mosquitoes swarmed in in troops. Mrs. M'Ginnis maddened by their attacks, got up, and going to the shelf upon which stood a **bottle** of spirits of camphor, rubbed her face and arms with the fluid, and then performed the same kind office for her husband, who lay snugly asleep. In the morning, upon waking, she was horrified to see a black man lying by the side of her. Jumping up, she seized a club and attacked him. M'Ginnis, on waking, was equally astonished at finding himself assaulted by an athletic negro woman, armed with a club, and a furious fight ensued. Mrs. M'Ginnis was a powerful woman, and it was not until both combatants were exhausted and terribly wounded that a pause ensued, and the combatants recognised each other. An investigation was then made, and it appeared that Mr. M'Ginnis had mistaken, in the dark, an **ink** bottle for that which contained the spirits of camphor. Hence the metamorphosis and its terrible results. The lesson taught by this history, for the veracity of which the *New York Times* vouches, should not be lost, and housekeepers should carefully avoid putting two **bottles** of the same form, but containing different liquids, upon a shelf or table together, especially if there are mosquitoes about, and one **bottle** contains

until both combatants were exhausted and terribly wounded that a pause ensued, and the combatants recognised each other. An investigation was then made, and it appeared that Mr. M'Ginnis had mistaken, in the dark, an **ink** bottle for that which contained the spirits of camphor. Hence the metamorphosis and its terrible results. The lesson taught by this history, for the veracity of which the *New York Times* vouches, should not be lost, and housekeepers should carefully avoid putting two **bottles** of the same form, but containing different liquids, upon a shelf or table together, especially if there are mosquitoes about, and one **bottle** contains **ink**.

THE BARNELL AGITATION

An example of the danger of placing bottles which, from their form, may be mistaken for each other, in contiguity, is afforded by a touching story which comes to us from Green Bay, in Wisconsin. At this place reside the M'Ginnises, a pair noted among their neighbours for mutual affection and good conduct. M'Ginnis is a local carrier by trade, and he one day appeared at work in a sadly battered state. His general appearance, in fact, suggested that he had been engaged in a difficulty with a locomotive engine running at full speed, and that subsequently all the coal dust in the tender had been poured over him. Of course, little was said to him on the subject, as he showed a disposition of

reticence by knocking down the first man who indelicately called public attention to him. As, upon Mrs. M'Ginnis appearing in public on the same day, it was found that her physiognomy had equally suffered, persons came to the conclusion that, unlikely as it appeared between so loving a couple, a family difficulty had arisen. It was not until some months later that Mr. M'Ginnis, in a diffusive moment, explained the cause of the appearances which had so puzzled and astonished his neighbours. Green Island, like most other parts of Wisconsin, is plagued with mosquitoes of a large and peculiarly vindictive kind. On the night in question the mosquito net at M'Ginnis's got out of order, and the mosquitoes swarmed in in troops. Mrs. M'Ginnis maddened by their attacks, got up, and going to the shelf upon which stood a bottle of spirits of campher, rubbed her face and arms with the fluid, and then performed the same kind office for her husband, who lay snugly asleep. In the morning, upon waking, she was horrified to see a black man lying by the side of her. Jumping up, she seized a club and attacked him. M'Ginnis, on waking, was equally astonished at finding himself assaulted by an athletic negro woman, armed with a club, and a furious fight ensued. Mrs. M'Ginnis was a powerful woman, and it was not until both combatants were exhausted and terribly wounded that a pause ensued, and the combatants recognised each other. An investigation was then made, and it appeared that Mr. M'Ginnis had mistaken, in the dark, an ink bottle for that which contained the spirits of camphor. Hence the metamorphosis and its terrible results. The lesson taught by this history, for the veracity of which the New York Times vouches, should not be lost, and house keepers should carefully avoid putting two bottles of the same form, but containing different liquids, upon a shelf or table together, especially if there are mosquitoes about, and bottle contains ink.

'The Latest Yarn from America', *Portsmouth Evening News* (20 Nov 1879), 3 [SY]

1880: A Camp Meeting

A Camp Meeting Difficulty.

A traveler on a Maryland steam boat tells this story to the *Forest and Stream*:

A clergyman, on his way home to Baltimore from camp meeting, was detailing to them some incidents of camp life. Among others was one of an old couple who had supplied themselves with a bottle of pennyroyal oil with which to keep off the mosquitos. They extinguished their light and retired, forgetting the antidote. The mosquitos were very bad, and after standing it as long as they could, the old lady got up and got a well-filled ink bottle instead of the oil, and gave the old gentleman a thorough lubricating with the liquid over face, hands and feet; she then anointed herself in like manner. They again assayed to court the drowsy god, but could only get an occasional nap. Finally the old lady got up and struck a light. Giving a glance at the bed she had just left, she beheld to her horror a colored "pusson," as she supposed, stretched in the place of her spouse. She quietly got the poker and nearly beat the old fellow's brains out before discovering her mistake. Later on in the night we discovered [the old couple to be on board the boat with us, he with his head nearly as big as a bale of hay, and she caring for him with the greatest solicitude.

A traveler on a Maryland steam boat tells this story to the *Forest and Stream*: A clergyman, on his way home to Baltimore from camp meeting, was detailing to them some incidents of camp life. Among others was one of an old couple who had supplied

themselves with a bottle of penny-royal oil with which to keep off the mosquitos. They extinguished their light and retired, forgetting the antidote. The mosquitos were very bad, and after standing it as long as they could, the old lady got up and got a well-filled ink bottle instead of the oil, and gave the old gentleman a thorough lubricating with the liquid over face, hands and feet; she then anointed herself in like manner. They again assayed to court the drowsy god, but could only get an occasional nap. Finally the old lady got up and struck a light. Giving a glance at the bed she had just left, she beheld to her horror a colored 'pusson', as she supposed, stretched in the place of her spouse. She quietly got the poker and nearly beat the old fellow's brains out before discovering her mistake. Later on in the night we discovered the old couple to be on board the boat with us, he with his head nearly as big as a bale of hay, and she caring for him with the greatest solicitude.

A Camp Meeting Difficulty, *The Shelby County Herald* [Shelbyville, MO], 22 Sep. 1880, ?? [BC]

1881: 'An absent-minded...'

AN absent-minded Congressman, who is in the habit of using a powerful hair tonic, forgot it one night not long ago. After he had put out the light and turned from side to side in a futile effort to court sleep, he suddenly remembered the tonic, and putting out his hand in the darkness seized a bottle and poured a plentiful supply on his head, rubbing it in vigorously with his hands. He fell asleep, and did not know until he saw his discolored hands in the morning that he had used ink instead of the hair wash. This led him to look in the mirror, and he was shocked to see the spectacle he presented with ink-stained brow, dyed hair, and cheeks and throat on which the black fluid had dripped. He has nearly rubbed all the hair and skin off his head and face since, but still traces of the smudge remain.

An absent-minded Congressman, who is in the habit of using a powerful hair tonic, forgot it one night not long ago. After he had put out the light and turned from side to side in a futile effort to court sleep, he suddenly remembered the tonic, and putting out his hand in the darkness seized a bottle and poured a plentiful supply on his head, rubbing it in vigorously with his hands. He fell asleep, and did not know until he saw his discolored hands in the morning that he had used ink instead of the hair wash. This led him to look in the mirror, and he was shocked to see the spectacle he presented with ink-stained brow, dyed hair, and cheeks and throat on which the black fluid had dripped.

He has nearly rubbed all the hair and skin off his head and face since, but still traces of the smudge remain.

‘An absent-minded Congressman...’, *The Cincinnati Enquirer* (29 Jan 1881), 12

1881: A Camp-Meeting Anecdote

A Camp-Meeting Anecdote.

An incident of camp-meeting life, detailed by a clergyman on a Baltimore steamboat, is thus reported in *Forest and Stream*:

An old couple had supplied themselves with a bottle of pennyroyal oil with which to keep off the mosquitoes. They extinguished their light and retired, forgetting the antidote.

The mosquitoes were very bad, and, after standing it as long as they could, the old lady got up and got a well-filled ink-bottle instead of the oil, and gave the old gentleman a thorough lubricating with the fluid, face, hands and feet; she then anointed herself in a like manner.

They again assayed to court the drowsy god, but could only get an occasional nap. Finally the old lady got up and struck a light. Giving a glance at the bed she had just left, she beheld, to her horror, a colored person, as she supposed, stretched in the place of her spouse.

She quietly got the poker, and beat the old fellow over the head before discovering her mistake. Later on in the night, we found the old couple on board the boat with us, he with his head nearly as big as a bale of hay, and she caring for him with the greatest solicitude.

An incident of camp-meeting life, detailed by a clergyman on a Baltimore steamboat, is thus reported in *Forest and Stream*:

An old couple had supplied themselves with a bottle of pennyroyal oil with which to keep off the mosquitoes. They extinguished their light, and retired, forgetting the antidote.

The mosquitoes were very bad, and, after standing it as long as they could, the old lady got up and got a well-filled ink-bottle instead of the oil, and gave the old gentleman a thorough lubricating with the fluid, face, hands and feet; she then anointed herself in a like manner-

They again assayed to court the drowsy god, but could only get an occasional nap. Finally the old lady got up and struck a light. Giving a glance at the bed she had just left, she beheld, to her horror, a colored person, as she supposed, stretched in the place of her spouse.

She quietly got the poker, and beat the old fellow over the head before discovering her mistake. Later on in the night, we found the old couple on board the boat with us, he with his head nearly as big as a bale of hay, and she caring for him with the greatest solicitude.

‘A Camp-Meeting Anecdote’, *The Troy Messenger* [AL], 17 March 1881, 7 [BC]

1883: Cut and Come Again

Some time ago it was recorded in the telegraphic dispatches that a young woman in one of the small towns of the country was greatly frightened upon awaking one morning to find that one of her legs had turned black. It was only after investigation that the trouble was discovered. The girl was afflicted with rheumatism, and being in great pain at night her attendant got up and secured what she supposed was the liniment bottle, but which turned out in the morning to have been the ink bottle. It is within the range of possibility that such a thing might have happened, though there are peculiarities in the shape of ink-bottles which make such a mistake next to impossible, even in the dark. But those who have heard the traditional story in which the incident figures will be very apt to doubt. The idea is not by any means a new one, for it forms the basis of a French-Latin story of the sixteenth century. The whole of the story could not be told, for it is about a suppositious monk and his mistress, but the incident of the ink is brought in in this way. While the monk, Glycas, is absent from his cell at prayers, the girl, Thais, gets up and feels around in the dark for a bottle of rose-water. She gets hold of a large ink bottle and paints herself from head to foot. Returned to his cell he is horrified to find a black woman. He rushes off in a panic, discloses the whole affair to the rest of the brethren, and is in great terror at the sin he has committed until the mystery is cleared up.

Some time ago it was recorded in the telegraphic dispatches that a young woman in one of the small towns of the country was greatly frightened upon waking one morning to find that one of her legs had turned black. It was only after investigation that the trouble was discovered. The girl was afflicted with rheumatism, and being in great pain at night her attendant got up and secured what she supposed was the liniment bottle, but which turned out in the morning to have been the ink bottle. It is within the range of possibility that such thing might have happened, though there are peculiarities in the shape of ink-bottles which make such mistake next to impossible, even in the dark. But those who have heard the traditional story in which the incident figures will be very apt to doubt. The idea is not by any means a new one, for it forms the basis of a French-Latin story of the sixteenth century. The whole of the story could not be told, for it is about suppositious monk and his mistress, but the incident of the ink is brought in this way. While the monk, Glycas, is absent from his call at prayers, the girl, Thais, gets up and feels around in the dark for a bottle of rose-water. She gets hold of a large ink bottle and paints herself from head to foot. Returned to his cell he was horrified to find a black woman. He rushes off in a panic, discloses the whole affair to the rest of the brethren, and is in great terror at the sin he has committed until the mystery is cleared up.

'Cut and Come Again', *The Cincinnati Enquirer* (Cincinnati, Ohio) · Sun, Aug 12, 1883 · Page 13 [CW, ground zero]

1892: Mind Cure

reported as having been cured by the earthquake.

It is said that a certain St. Louis man who was greatly afraid of the cholera, when that disease threatened to invade this country some years ago, never went to bed at night, without having upon the stand at his bedside a bottle of cholera liniment which was supposed to cure the cholera by application over the stomach. Waking up one night with a sudden pain in his stomach, he aroused his wife with the exclamation, "Give me the liniment quick,—the cholera has got me!" The good woman handed her husband a bottle which, in the dark, she supposed to be the cholera medicine, and the poor man was soon relieved of his pain and his alarm, and fell asleep. The morning light revealed the fact that the good woman in her nervous haste had given her husband an ink bottle, and that the cholera patient had been cured by an application of Arnold's writing fluid!

It is said that a certain St. Louis man who was greatly afraid of the cholera, when that disease threatened to invade this country some years ago, never went to bed at night, without having upon the stand at his bedside a bottle of cholera liniment which was supposed to cure the cholera by application over the stomach. Waking up one night with a sudden pain in his stomach, he aroused his wife with the exclamation, 'Give me the liniment quick, the cholera has got me!' The good woman handed her husband a bottle which, in the dark, she supposed to be the cholera medicine, and the poor man was soon relieved of his pain and his alarm, and fell asleep. The morning light revealed the fact that the good woman in her nervous haste had given her husband an ink bottle, and that the cholera patient had been cured by an application of Arnold's writing fluid!

'Mind Cure', Good Health 27 (1892), 150-151 [BTB]

1892: Modern Instances of Black Art

Modern Instance of Black Art.
 A Devils Lake man woke up in the night and complained of rheumatism. His wife rubbed him plentifully with liniment. He felt better at once and went to sleep again. The next morning he found his wife had got the ink bottle instead of the liniment, and he now sleeps between two blotting pads.—
 Minneapolis Journal.

A Devils Lake man woke up in the night and complained of rheumatism. His wife rubbed him plentifully with liniment. He felt better at once and went to sleep again. The next morning he found his wife had got the ink bottle instead of the liniment, and he now sleeps between two blotting pads.

'Modern Instance of Black Art', *Davenport Sunday Democrat* [Iowa], 25 Feb. 1894, 3 [BC]

1892: Turned Black in the Night

Coventry Times - Wednesday 31 August 1892

< Page 5 of 8

Image © Reach PLC. Image created courtesy of THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD.

Among the h it was thought e given, printing, joinery, plumbing.	urgencies, 4; pay patients, 0; private, 0; children's ward, 2..... 10 Discharged—Cured, 6; relieved, 0; <i>in statu</i> <i>quo</i> , 0; deaths, 0..... 6	high wages going into the pockets of a few only.
in barrels question tallers some time in the <i>Manchester</i> respondent. The lad if any readers rewers are exempt he Weights and plied to the trade ated to contain a 36 gallons. It is rrels do not con- stated to contain. barrel should be of Weights and the official stamp ty to contain the t such is not the those engaged in ly a barrel will be measure. This of the berseller and brewer. I cannot ny way exempts the sooner the ampton the better, persons engaged in ct to the law and	Number now in the Hospital 43 Out-patients attended during the week 208 G.G. Passox, House Surgeon.	TURNED BLACK IN A NIGHT. Madame Martin, living in an outer suburb of Paris, recently experienced one of the most extraordinary shocks that have ever startled a human being. On awakening from her slumbers on Thursday morning, says the correspondent of the <i>Daily Telegraph</i> , she was horrified to find that her husband's face had turned completely black during the night. Panting with terror, the woman hastily threw on her clothes and rushed, haggard and unkempt, to the office of the Comj missary of Police. There she astonished a member of the "Force" by shouting in his ear, "Come quickly! My husband has been turned into a negro during last night's storm!" The policeman, regarding Madame Martin as a maniac, took her to the Commissary's clerk, and to this official she also related the transformation scene, but in a perfectly cool and collected manner. The clerk, thinking after all that some phenomenon had happened through the agency of electricity, put on his hat and accompanied Madame Martin to her domicile. There the husband was found wide-awake, but looking as if he had been carefully lamp-blacked before going to bed. Explanations followed, and it was ascertained that Madame Martin, who is a devout Catholic, had, during the night of a terrible thunderstorm, flung the contents of what she considered to be a bottle of holy water on the bed and on her husband's face, thinking thereby to drive away the lightning demon. The bottle contained common ink, and hence the metamorphosis in the original Caucasian colour of the worthy M. Martin, which so startled his spouse and caused her to invoke the aid of the police in her bewilderment.
the Coventry Indus- d Building Society, Thursday night, the erous condition. irman) presided. having been taken ving their adoption, on having such a great reason that	Good accounts have been received of the progress made by Dr. R. W. Dale. He is still at Llanbedr, near Harlech; but will, in a short time, go on a visit to some friends on the Menai Straits. It is expected that he will return to Birmingham about the middle of September. On Wednesday Isaac Jones, living at 27, West Orchard, Coventry, was treated at the Coventry and North Warwickshire Hospital for an accident which had befallen him whilst following his work as a shoemaker at Mr. Stanton's, Market Hall. He was repairing a pair of boots when the knife he was using slipped and penetrated his left leg. He was detained in the institution. George Poole, Carpenter's Lane, Foleshill, also met with an accident. He was assisting in some excavating operations in the Rose and Crown Yard, High Street, when he fell down a hole about twelve feet deep. He was also treated at the hospital.	
	COVENTRY SAVINGS BANK.—Weekly Report.—Amount received from the 22nd of August to the 29th of August, in 223 deposits, £895 15s. 9d. Amount repaid from ditto ditto, in 175 sums, £982 11s. 2d. Amount now invested with the Government, £220,762 10s. 1d. Amount now invested in Supplementary Investment De-	

Madame Martin, living in an outer suburb of Paris, recently experienced one of the most extraordinary shocks that have ever startled a human being. On awakening from her slumbers on Thursday morning, says the correspondent of the *Daily Telegraph*, she was horrified to find that her husband's face had turned completely black during the night. Panting with terror, the woman hastily threw on her clothes and rushed, haggard and unkempt, to the office of the Commissary of Police. There she astonished a member of the 'Force' by shouting in his ear, 'Come quickly! My husband has been turned into a negro during last night's storm!' The policeman, regarding Madame Martin manias, took her to the Commissary's clerk, and to this official she also related the transformation scene, but in a perfectly cool and collected ed manner. The clerk, thinking after all that some phenomenon had happened through the agency of electricity, put on his bat and accompanied Madame Martin to her domicile. There the husband was found wide-awake, but looking as if he had been carefully lamp-blacked before going to bed.

Explanations followed, and it was ascertained that Madama Martin, who is a devout Catholic, had, during the night of a terrible thunderstorm, flung the contents of what she considered to be a bottle of holy water on the bed and on her husband's face, thinking thereby to drive away the lightning demon. The bots contained common, and hence the metamorphosis in the original Caucasian colour of the worthy M. Martin, which so startled his spouse and caused her to invoke the aid of the police in her bewilderment.

'Turned Black in the Night', *Coventry Times* (31 Aug 1892), 5 [SY]

1892: A good lady

Northern Guardian (Hartlepool) - Monday 29 August 1892 < Page 2 of 4 >

Public domain

Northern Guardian (Hartlepool) - Monday 29 August 1892 < Page 3 of 4 >

Public domain

A good lady in Paris awoke the other morning to find that her husband's face had turned completely black during the night. Thinking the phenomenon to be the result of a severe thunderstorm, she rushed to the nearest police station, and called the officer to the house, by which time the husband was awake and swearing somewhat. Still, the lady's story was true. The man's face was as black as night, and had it not been for an accidental discovery he would, undoubtedly, have made his fortune as a specimen of the awful effects of electricity upon the complexion. The secret of the transformation, however, was brought to light. The lady was a good Catholic, and alarmed at the fierceness of the storm during the night, she had taken what she supposed to be a bottle of holy water from the mantel-shelf and dashed it on to the bed. But she handled a bottle of ink by mistake, and the result was that the roses in her husband's cheeks were very effectually blotted out. This story is taken from the Daily Telegraph.

‘A good lady...’, *Northern Guardian* (29 Aug 1892), 2 [SY]

1892: Lightning Plays...

Million - Saturday 17 September 1892

< Page 7 of 12 >

Image © THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD. ALL RIGHTS RESERVED.

Million - Saturday 17 September 1892

< Page 7 of 12 >

Image © THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD. ALL RIGHTS RESERVED.

Lightning plays curious tricks sometimes, but it has never yet transformed a white man into a n____. A Frenchman, however, had a narrow escape the other day. He was sleeping peacefully during a terrible storm, when his wife flung over his face what she believed to be the contents of a bottle of holy water to drive away the lightning demon. When morning dawned she was horrified to discover that her husband was as black as a n____. She screamed and rushed off for the indispensable policeman. The worthy gendarme found that the lady's husband was as black as she had reported him to be, and was not a little puzzled thereby. He called a brother policeman to his aid, and they endeavoured to account for the transformation. Just then the policeman's eye lighted upon the bottle of holy water with which the sleeping Benedict had been piously drenched. The first glance at it threw him into convulsions of laughter. The good lady had sprinkled her husband with a bottle of ink !

'Lightning Plays', *Million* (17 Sep 1892), 7 [SY]

1895: Talk of the Town

[BC] 'Billy the Bear,' than whom there is no man in the west better known, is sometimes troubled with rheumatism and has a remedy for the same which he keeps in a small vial and applies externally. The other night, when the air was full of moisture, Billy's rheumatism began to pound his shoulder most unmercifully. It awakened him along toward morning, 'ere dawn appeared in the east, and he lay in bed and suffered as long as he could bear it and then awakened his better half and explained the situation. She arose and groped around in the uncertain light for the liniment. She finally found the

bottle and applied the contents vigorously to Billy's aching shoulders. After giving it a good rubbing Billy murmured ‘ Ah! that feels better,’ and rolled over and went to sleep. When he awoke in the morning he discovered that his good frau had by mistake taken the ink bottle instead of the liniment bottle and Billy had a shoulder as black as the ace of spades. But it cured the rheumatism, which was the consummation most devoutly to be wished.

‘Talk of the Town’, *Chadron Record* [Nebraska] (7 Jun 1895), 4 [BC]

1895: Mildred

Daily Gazette for Middlesbrough - Friday 07 June 1895

< Page 4 of 4 >

Image © Reach PLC. Image created courtesy of THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD.

CHAPTER XII. (CONTINUED.)

Blinded by her sister, Lilian had as much expected to be the future wife of Lawrence Thornton as to see the next day's sun, and had never thought it possible for him to choose another; so when she saw his position with Mildred and heard the words "Lilian can never be my wife" she sank on the carpet and fainted.

"Now, I'll be hanged," said the Judge, "if this ain't a little the greatest performance; but go right on, have your say out. I'll tend to her;" and bursting into the library, he caught up the ink-bottle instead of the camphor. "A little thrown in her face will fetch her to. Camphor is good for hysterics," he said; and hurrying back, he would have deluged Lilian with ink if Mildred had not pushed him away.

Whether Lawrence would have had his say out or not was not proved, for Mildred sprang to Lilian's side, and lifting her head on her lap, asked if she were ill.

"No, no," moaned Lilian—"not ill, but I wish that I were dead. Oh, Mildred, how could you she meant, and he was alone. Lawrence had come to tell his father did not wish to tell Lawrence about the accident and Judge Howell and could be managed to drag in the Albany in the morning, and Monday.

"I can tell him then," and if she refuse me it would not to know it."

Thus deciding he bade and when next morning a down to breakfast he was told Uncle Robert had started Albany.

(To be continued)

SIBYL'S IN OR, THE MISS

By the Author of "TRIXY,"

‘ Now, I'll be hanged,’ said the Judge, ‘ if this ain't a little the greatest performance; but go right on, have your say out. I'll tend to her;’ and bursting into the library, he caught up the ink bottle instead of the camphor. ‘ A little thrown in her face will fetch her to. Camphor is good for hysterics,’ he said; and hurrying back, he would have deluged Lilian with ink if Mildred had not pushed him away.

‘Mildred’, *Daily Gazette for Middlesbrough* (7 Jun 1895), 4 [SY]

1896: The friends...

deadly ptomaine lurked.

The friends of a Chicago man had him arrested on the charge of insanity for appearing on the street with his face blackened with ink. He explained, however, that he had mistaken ink for cologne, as he always rubbed cologne on his face before going to call on the girl he was in love with.

The friends of a Chicago man had him arrested on the charge of insanity for appearing on the street with his face blackened with ink. He explained, however, that he had mistaken ink for Cologne, as he always rubbed cologne on his face before going to call on the girl he was in love with.

‘The friends...’, *Sun Journal* (6 Jun 1899), 4 [BTB]

1899: Pastor

Fife Free Press - Saturday 05 August 1899

< Page 2 of 8 >

Image © THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD. ALL RIGHTS RESERVED.

<p>THORN.</p> <p>encamped at al spe within the dist⁺ished party 'enc⁺re, while the e crow⁺ of spectators. ficers⁺ be present anky⁺ Edinburgh ; th Fort; Captain and ers of H.M.S. Oale- Hilmour and party ; s; Captain and Mrs d Mrs Bromilaw, St mond, St Andrews ; : Weir, Fife Miners, allingall, Sweetbank ; Strathore: Mr and</p>	<p>PASTOR JACOB PRIMMER AT KIRKCALDY BATTERY.</p> <p>SOME CURIOUS TALES.</p> <p>Pastor Jacob Primmer addressed an audience of fully 2000 at the Battery, Kirkcaldy, on Tuesday night. He spoke for fully an hour-and-a-half, and as usual tickled his large audience with some of his "funny," pithy sayings. Mr Primmer commenced his address by keel-hauling a couple of Glasgow newspapers for belittling the attendances at several of his meetings. At one meeting in Paisley, where, he stated, the audience numbered 10,000, one newspaper put it at 2000; while on Glasgow Green the multitude at his meeting on Sabbath was estimated at 15,000, and it was published as 3000 in one paper and 4000 in another. In Eng.</p>	<p>KIRKCALDY HIGH S</p> <p>RESULTS OF LEAVING CERTIFICATE</p> <p>ENGLISH.—Higher Grade—James beth Horne, Eloise Meroer, Willis Wallace, Alexander Welsh, May Yul —James Anderson, Jeanie Barnet, Jo Baxter, John Baxter, Alex. Bennet, Jessie Cairns, Mabel Campbell, P John Chapman, Grant Clark, O David Farmer, Thomas Grieve, May Henderson, Marguerite Key, Julia Morgan, Elizabeth Morrison, Art Reid, Jessie Spears, Christina T Tulloch, Joseph Waddell.</p> <p>LATIN.—Higher Grade—James White. Lower Grade—James Brow hall, David Farmer, Mary Grant.</p>
--	--	---

To show you that imagination is a wonderfully powerful factor, I read the other day of a man suffering from spasms of the heart, who was in the habit of rubbing on [50] a particular kind of liniment. When the pain came on, he would jump out of bed, get hold of the bottle and rub this liniment in until the pain went away. This happened to him one night; he got out of bed in the dark and seized a bottle and rubbed himself thoroughly, and in five minutes the pain went away, and he went to sleep again. Next morning he found he had been operation with the ink bottle. (Loud laughter).

‘Annual Meeting of the National Anti-Vivisection Society’, *Zoophilist* 19 (1899), 45-52 [SY]

1901: A Slight Mistake

Weekly Dispatch (London) - Sunday 15 September 1901

< Page 20 of 20 >

Image © Reach PLC. Image created courtesy of THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD.

During a recent thunderstorm at Paterson, N. J., a Mrs William Donoghue jumped out of bed, and, getting what she supposed was a bottle of holy water, sprinkled the sleeping members of her family. When they awoke in the morning and saw themselves in a mirror they were startled by their streaked faces. The woman, in the dark, had picked up by mistake a bottle of ink.

‘A Slight Mistake’, *Weekly Dispatch* (15 Sep 1901), 20 [SY]

1902: Railway Yarns

Image © THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD. ALL RIGHTS RESERVED.

RAILWAY YARNS. - II

(By K. R.)

"Look here old man, I don't mind trying to spin a yarn now and then, when in the humour—but I object to being 'turned on' like a beer tap—whenever it suits Your Majesty to feel disposed to be talked asleep—Oh, it's very fine your saying you like hearing a yarn, and that you *don't* go to sleep—but I never can tell a yarn well, at any time, but even the best story-teller shies at being 'turned on.' However, this once I'll agree to the process, and endeavour to tell you one of my many experiences, one which may be described as a combination of the tragic and the comic.

"In 1864 the railway between Mumpur and Lagote was in course of construction. Things generally went in an easy, happy-go-lucky style. The class of Englishmen required for such appointments as overseers and platelayers were few and far between—those there were, to a man almost, drank to excess, but they had to be leniently dealt with, for others were not to be found to replace them if they were dismissed. The men employed on the Mumpur-Lagote line were as bad as any—every one of them drank to excess, and freely followed other customs of the country—and but little was said to them, so they went from bad to worse. One very hot morning in May, the District Engineer of No. 2 District got a wire from Brown his platelayer at Likawasti,

and in his sleep he must have rubbed the brilliant scarlet ink all over his face. Seeing all, that we four had seen, and making allowances for Mr. Brown's shaky condition at daybreak, we were *not* surprised at the conclusion Mr. Brown had come to, before he despatched his wire to Baynes—so we forgave him for giving us all as disagreeable a journey as I ever remember taking. We got back to Lagote for a late dinner and over our iced drinks, which we thoroughly enjoyed, had a good laugh at the way we had all been taken in."

REVIEWS.

ANOTHER WAR BOOK.

Pictures of War: Archibald Constable and Co., London.—Mr. John Stuart in his volume, entitled "Pictures of War," reproduces most of the newspaper letters which he wrote to the *Morning Post*, as its war correspondent, before, during, and immediately after, the siege of Ladysmith, and during Mahou's march to Mafeking. These letters induced Sir Wilfrid Lawson (whom Mr. Stuart tartly describes as "that artist in solemn impertinence") to describe, in the House of Commons, the author of them as a "human demon disguised as a war correspondent." When it is remembered that Mr. Stuart had lived for some years under Mr. Kruger's "benign Government," and had come in

Image © THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD. ALL RIGHTS RESERVED.

the District Engineer of No. 2 District got a wire from Brown his platelayer at Likawasti, telling him that Rogers, another of his Inspectors, had either been murdered or committed suicide in his—Brown's—house at Likawasti, and begging that he, the District Engineer, would run down at once, bringing a Doctor, and a Policeman. Baynes—the Engineer—and I were then living together, at Lagote—both of us being bachelors. We immediately arranged for an engine, for Likawasti was 70 miles away, and having got hold of the Civil Surgeon, and the Police Superintendent, we started—travelling in a guards van—for there were no carriages built then. The rate of speed was very low, for the line was much after the pattern of a cork screw, and an engine could only secure safety over it by crawling slowly along—and so it was quite three in the afternoon before we sighted the station of Likawasti, the scene of the tragedy. We all went over at once to the Platelayer's bungalow, and there discovered Mr. Brown, the sender of the telegram, very fast asleep. We soon roused him up, but he was in a very fuddled condition, and it took a good few minutes, and a bucket of water or two, before we could get anything out of him. He told us how Rogers, his next door neighbour at Gam, 12 miles away—had turned up, unexpectedly, on his trolley the evening before, how they had dined together, and between them had consumed three bottles of brandy by 10 p. m. They then retired to bed. Rogers sleeping in a little room, which Brown was pleased to call his office—how he,

Brown was pleased to call his office—how he, Brown—had got up just as dawn was coming and went in to see how his friend was—and had found him, and the pillow, and sheets saturated in blood, and Rogers lifeless. He rushed back to his own room and “just to steady my nerves” swallowed half a bottle of brandy—wrote and despatched the telegram to Baynes—took another long pull at the brandy, and dropped on to his bed and into the deep sleep—from which we had roused him. We at once saw that any hope there may have been, early in the morning of preventing poor Rogers’ bleeding to death, was now all gone—so we, being directed by Brown to the room in which the corpse lay, entered—it was a low roofed small verandah room, and even now was almost dark. The sight that met our eyes was a distinctly disagreeable one. The body was lying with its knees almost touching the chin, and one hand was hard gripping the pillow. The sheets and pillow were a brilliant scarlet, and the face of the corpse was besmeared all over with blood—a gruesome sight truly—and I commenced to have more of a fellow feeling for Mr. Brown in his anxiety to ‘steady my nerves’ than I had at first. Thackwell—the Doctor—more used to horrid sights than I was—walked straight up to the bed, pulled off the sheet and rolled the body on to its back. “Get out, who the devil are you a shoving of” shouted the supposed corpse,—and Mr. Rogers—very much alive—but still a disgusting sight—sat up in bed, rubbed his eyes—stared at us—and rubbed

rubbed his eyes—stared at us—and rubbed his eyes again! There was nothing wrong with the man beyond a bad go of hot coppers! Thackwell, however, discovered an empty quart bottle in the bed, and taking it to the one tiny window in the room, read on its label ‘Best Scarlet Ink.’

“A further interview with Mr. Brown, who had grown rapidly sober, quite cleared up the mystery. It appears that after Rogers had got to bed, Brown, on hospitality bent, took into his room a bottle of brandy—which he put upon the chimney piece with the remark ‘Here’s a bottle for you old fellow, real three star—if you want a drink during the night.’ Mr. Rogers, who had already imbibed more than he could decently carry, very shortly after Brown’s departure decided he *did* want a drink: so out of bed he stumbled, and in the dark found the chimney piece and felt along it, and finding a glass bottle, seized and took it back to bed with him, and lying on his back commenced to take ‘pulls’ at the ‘Three star.’ Already so drunk was he that he failed to know that he was drinking red ink instead of his much loved ‘Hennessy’! Sleep overcame him, and he fell back, still clutching the bottle on his chest—over-toppled the bottle and emptied its contents on Mr. Roger’s neck, pillow, and sheets

and in his sleep he must have rubbed the brilliant scarlet ink all over his face. Seeing all, that we four had seen, and making allowances for Mr. Brown's shaky condition at daybreak, we were *not* surprised at the conclusion Mr. Brown had come to, before he despatched his wire to Baynes —so we forgave him for giving us all as disagreeable a journey as I ever remember taking. We got back to Lagote for a late dinner and over our iced drinks, which we thoroughly enjoyed, had a good laugh at the way we had all been taken in."

In 1864 the railway between Mumpur and Lagote was in course of construction. Things generally went in an easy, happy-go-lucky style. The class of Englishmen required for such appointments as overseers and plate layers were few and far between those there were, to a man almost, drank to excess, but they had to be leniently dealt with, for others were not to be found to replace them if they were dismissed. The men employed on the Mumpur-Lagote line were as bad as any- every one of them drank to excess, and freely followed other customs of the country and but little was said to them, so they went from bad to worse. One very hot morning in May, the District Engineer of No. 2 District got the District Engineer of No. 2 District got a wire from Brown his platelayer at Likawasti, telling him that Rogers, another of his inspectors, had either been murdered or committed suicide in his Brown's house at Likawasti, and begging that he, the District Engineer, would rush down at once, bringing a Doctor, and a Policeman. Baynes-the Engineer-and I were then living together, at Lagote-both of us being bachelors. We immediately arranged for an engine, for Likawasti was 70 miles away, and having got hold of the Civil Surgeon, and the Police Superintendent, we started-travelling in a guards van for there were no carriages built then. The rate of speed was very low, for the line was much after the pattern of a corkscrew, and an engine could only secure safety over it by crawling slowly along-and so it was quite three in the afternoon before we sighted the station of Likawasti, the scene of the tragedy. We all went over at once to the Platelayer's bungalow, and there discovered Mr. Brown, the sender of the telegram, very fast asleep. We soon roused him up, but he was in a very fuddled condition, and it took a good few minutes, and a bucket of water or two, before we could get anything out of him. He told us how Rogers, his next door neighbour at Gam, 12 miles away-had turned up, unexpectedly, on his trolley the evening before, how they had dined together, and between them had consumed three bottles of brandy by 10 p. m. They then retired to

bed. Rogers sleeping in a little room, which Brown was pleased to call his office-how he, Brown-had got up just as dawn was coming and went in to see how his friend was-and had found him, and the pillow, and sheets saturated in blood, and Rogers lifeless. He rushed back to his own room and 'just to steady my nerves' swallowed half a bottle of brandy-wrote and despatched the telegram to Baynes-took another long pull at the brandy, and dropped on to his bed and into the deep sleep-from which we had roused him. We at once saw that any hope there may have been, early in the morning of preventing poor Rogers' bleeding to death, was now all gone- so we, being directed by Brown to the room in which the corpse lay, entered it was a low roofed small verandah room, and even now was almost dark. The sight that met our eyes was a distinctly disagreeable one. The body was lying with its knees almost touching the chin, and one hand was hard gripping the pillow. The sheets and pillow were a brilliant scarlet, and the face of the corpse was besmeared all over with blood-a gruesome sight truly and I commenced to have more of a fellow feeling for Mr. Brown in his anxiety to steady my nerves than I had at first. Thackwell-the Doctor-more used to horrid sights than I was-walked straight up to the bed, pulled off the sheet and rolled the body on to its back. 'Get out. who the devil are you a shoving of' shouted the supposed corpse, and Mr. Rogers-very much alive- but still a disgusting sight-sat up in bed, rubbed his eyes-stared at us-and rubbed his eyes again! There was nothing wrong with the man beyond a bad go of hot coppers! Thackwell, however, discovered an empty quart bottle in the bed, and taking it to the one tiny window in the room, read on its label Best Scarlet Ink.' 'A further interview with Mr. Brown, who had grown rapidly sober, quite cleared up the mystery. It appears that after Rogers had got to bed, Brown, on hospitality bent, took into his room a bottle of brandy-which he put upon the chimney piece with the remark Here's a bottle for you old fellow, real three star-if you want a drink during the night. Mr. Rogers, who had already imbibed more than he could decently carry, very shortly after Brown's departure decided he did want a drink: so out of bed he stumbled, and in the dark found the chimney piece and felt along it, and finding a glass bottle, seized and took it back to bed with him, and lying on his back commenced to take pulls at the Three star. Already so drunk was he that he failed to know that he was drinking red ink instead of his much loved Hennessy! Sleep overcame him, and he fell back, still clutching the bottle on his chest -over-toppled the bottle and emptied its contents on Mr. Roger's neck, pillow, and sheets and in his sleep he must, have rubbed the brilliant scarlet ink all over his face. Seeing all, that we four had seen, and making allowances for Mr. Brown's shaky condition at daybreak, we were not surprised at the conclusion Mr. Brown had come to, before he despatched his wire to Baynes-so we for- gave him for giving us all as disagreeable a journey as I ever remember taking. We got back to Lagote for a late dinner and over our iced drinks, which we thoroughly enjoyed, had a good laugh at the way we had all been taken in.'

'Railway Yarns II', *Civil & Military Gazette* (3 May 1902), 5

Cured by Faith: 1902

Cornishman - Thursday 28 August 1902

< Page 7 of 8 >

Image © Reach PLC. Image created courtesy of THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD.

The owner of an estate in Schleswig woke up the other night with toothache. His groans awoke his wife, who told him to take a bottle of brandy which was standing on the window sill and rub some on his cheek. He used some of the contents of the bottle he found and soon fell asleep. Great was the lady's amazement when in the morning she found her husband's face and the bedclothes all black. In the dark he had taken a bottle of ink instead of the brandy he was searching for!

'Cured by Faith', *Cornishman* (28 Aug 1902), 7 [SY]

The man...: 1902

Bristol Magpie - Thursday 04 September 1902

< Page 7 of 20 >

Image © THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD. ALL RIGHTS RESERVED.

The man who was reported to have swallowed a bottle of ink one night by mistake, instead of a dose of toothache tincture, while suffering from a bad attack of his grinders, must have looked very 'black' at his wife in the morning.

'The man...?', *Bristol Magpie* (4 Sep 1902), 7 [SY]

1908: A Young Lady's

Image © THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD. ALL RIGHTS RESERVED.

's Dilemma.

in had for some time been suffering complicated disease, of which none of us had been able to cure him. He was a friend to consult one Dr. Heavyweight, a specialist in this disease. At the time he was told that the doctor's fee was

A Young Lady's Unpleasant Experience

A fashionable and charming young lady in the West End of London has had a painful experience. She was upstairs, and had just turned out her light when she heard a caller ask for her. She made a dive for her powder-puff in the dark, and dusted her face with powder. Instead, however, of putting the "puff" into the powder box she put it into the powdered charcoal used as tooth powder, and dusted it freely over her face. Then she went to the parlour and found a distinguished stranger, on whom she was anxious to make an impression. He appeared rather nonplussed at her looks, but being a man of the world, which means a man wise enough not to tell a woman her faults, he said nothing. She sat and chatted gracefully, and had a delightful evening. As soon as he had gone she rushed to the mirror, as every-girl does when her beau leaves. She gave one scream and went off into hysterics, as her mistake in the dark had given her the make-up of an amateur Christy minstrel.

crowd outside.
"As nearly as I
that night must
Godfrey ever dire

New-Year's

Lawyer Crabbe
as much as his
liquor. On the d
had determined t
of a holiday wer
by announcing :-
"Well, gentlem
I hope you'll all
round."

A buzz went r
had heard arigh
One youth only
mering a bit, he
be excused.

"Well, if you
thing, I suppose

A fashionable and charming young lady in the West End of London has had a painful experience. She was upstairs, and had just turned out her light when she heard a caller ask for her. She made a dive for her powder-puff in the dark, and dusted her face with powder. Instead, however, of putting the 'puff' into the powder box she put it into the powdered charcoal used as tooth powder, and dusted it freely over her face. Then she went to the parlour and found a distinguished stranger, on whom she was anxious to make an impression. He appeared rather nonplussed at her looks, but being a man of the world, which means a man wise enough not to tell a woman her faults, he said nothing. She sat and chatted gracefully, and had a delightful evening. As soon as he had gone she rushed to the mirror, as every-girl does when her beau leaves. She gave one scream and went off into hysterics, as her mistake in the dark had given her the make-up of an amateur Christy minstrel.

'A Young Lady's Unpleasant Experience', *Sheffield Weekly Telegraph* (26 Dec 1908), 9 [SY]

1912: A Startling Mistake

One time there was a lady who had been working hard all day, for she was going to have company that evening.

She told her son to take a pitcher of water to her room.

Her little girl, three years old, was playing upstairs in her room and got hold of an ink bottle and emptied the contents into the pitcher.

The lady hurried up stairs to wash her face and to dress before entering the parlor, when the doorbell rang. She hastily wiped her hands and face and went to answer the bell.

The minister stood in the doorway. He laughed till he cried, and she couldn't imagine what he was laughing at, but when she got a chance to look into the glass—O! ye gods and

little fishes! Her face, her white waist, her hands, and her white skirt streaked with black, inky stripes. were

She said, 'I must have mistaken ink for rain water,' and fled into the kitchen.

VERONICA ROCHLEAU, Age 11, North Franklin.

Veronica Rochleau, 'A Startling Mistake', *Norwich Bulletin* (22 Aug 1912), 4 [BTB]

1921: Brooks

A JOKE ON GRANDPA

Grandpa Oscar Nicholson of Greensfork, fell down stairs and sprained his ankle. That night grandpa went to bed and after awhile his ankle began to hurt very bad, so he got up and put some supposed-to-be liniment on it. Then it got easy and grandpa went back to bed. The next morning he looked at his ankle and it was all black. He called grandma and she said he was mortifying and wanted to send for the doctor, but in looking for the liniment she found grandpa had used black ink instead. Good-bye. —Howard Brooks, Richmond, Ind.

Grandpa Oscar Nicholson of Greensfork, fell downstairs and sprained his ankle. That night grandpa went to bed and after awhile his ankle began to hurt very bad, so he got up and put some supposed-to-be liniment on it. Then it got easy and grandpa went back to bed. The next morning he looked at his ankle and it was all black. He called grandma and she said he was mortifying and wanted to send for the doctor, but in looking for the liniment she found grandpa had used black ink instead. Good-bye. - Howard Brooks, Richmond, Ind.

Howard Brooks, 'A Joke on Grandpa', *Palladium-Item* (27 Aug 1921), 13 [BTB]

1938: 'Chatterbox'

Recently a Manhattan woman was caring for a friend's small son, when he developed a case of croup. At once she reached on her stand for a bottle of medicine the friend had left for her to apply to the boy's throat and chest. Soon he was fast asleep but imagine said lady's dismay the next morning as she looked at the child and his pajamas, they were dark blue. Upon investigating she found she had used ink instead of the ointment left.

Recently a Manhattan woman was caring for a friend's small son, when he developed a case of croup. At once she reached on her stand for a bottle of medicine the friend had left for her to apply to the boy's throat and chest. Soon he was fast asleep but imagine said lady's dismay the next morning as she looked at the child and his pajamas, they were dark blue. Upon investigating she found she had used ink instead of the ointment left.

'Chatterbox', *The Manhattan Mercury* (8 Oct 1938), 2 [BTB]

1957: A Lafayette...

those bomb-type squirters so much alike.

A Lafayette woman blushing admits that while reaching for a jar of Vapo-rub in the dark, she got a bottle of black ink instead. It wasn't only a lot thinner, it was also darker, but the containers felt the same in the dark.

A Lafayette woman blushing admits that while reaching for a jar of Vapo-rub in the dark, she got a bottle of black ink instead. It wasn't only a lot thinner, it was also darker, but the containers felt the same in the dark.

‘A Lafayette woman...’, *Muncie Evening Press* (22 Feb 1957), 4 [BTB]

1973: The August...

The August issue of *Ladies Home Journal* carries an article by J.B. West, a former White House chief usher during the Eisenhower administration. He relates how Mamie, suffering from a head cold, reached in the dark for what she thought was a jar of nose drops, but got a bottle of ink instead. When the drops didn't seem to work, Mamie added more. She and Ike were covered with ink when they awakened in the morning. Sounds like the guy I heard about who grabbed a can of spray paint thinking it was deodorant.

‘The August issue of...’, *Quad-City Times* (23 Jul 1973), 8 [BTB, ed notes ‘a can of spray paint thinking it was deodorant’... has UL potential.]

1978: ‘Jane’

Indelibly Beautiful

You probably don't know Jane, but you know someone like her. Someone whom merely to think of brings a smile. When I'm stuck in traffic or listening to a boring speaker or can't get to sleep, I think about Jane . . . about the time the lights went out and she reached into her dresser drawer for her face lotion, and when the lights came back on she discovered she'd rubbed blue/black ink instead of skin freshner all over her face.

You probably don't know Jane, but you know someone like her. Someone whom merely to think of brings a smile. When I'm stuck in traffic or listening to a boring speaker or can't get to sleep, I think about Jane... about the time the lights went out and she reached into her dresser drawer for her face lotion, and when the lights came back on she discovered she'd rubbed blue/black ink instead of skin freshner all over her face.

Ina Hughs, 'Jane: She's Life's Best Banana Peel', *The Charlotte Observer* (17 Feb 1978), 28 [BTB]

Appendix 1: The Holy Water Joke

Illustrated London News - Saturday 24 December 1853

< Page 18 of 40 >

Image © Illustrated London News Group. Image created courtesy of THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD.

duly appreciated by his niece.

“One night,” she goes on, “we emptied a bottle of ink into the holy-water vessel at the door of the church. When the sisters came together for matins, at two in the morning, it was their custom, as they knew the place by heart, to dispense with lights, except one small lamp, which lit the *benétier* only feebly. Each crossed herself with the holy water, and went in without noticing the effect it produced. But as the day dawned toward the close of the service, each sister saw all the others striped in such a singular way that first one, and then another, began to laugh, and the service was interrupted. No one doubted for a moment that this piece of mischief was done by some pupil, but it was never discovered which it was.

“A few days later we tried some-

Peter Burger contributes this Dutch example

Kluchtige Gebeurtenis

Te Amsterdam hadden eenige jeugdige pretmakers ter linker- en rechterzijde bij de deur van de kerk in het eene wijwater- bakje een flesch inkt en in het andere eenige flesschen Eau d'Anvers gestort. Men belde voor de mis, de personen die ter rechter- zijde binnenkwamen doopten hun vingers in de heerlijke parfumerie en waren over de

heerlijke geur van het water verbaasd dat zij geheiligd waanden, de personen die ter linkerzijde binnenkwamen doopten hunne vingers in de inkt en daar de kerk in het duister gehuld was, merkten zij niet op, dat hun voorhoofd met twee of drie inktvlakken besproeid was. Eene bejaarde dame die dit water zoo heerlijk gevonden had, doopte haar zakdoek in de wijwaterbak. Maar in plaats van door de rechterdeur te gaan ging zij door de linkerdeur, zij wrijft er zich het voorhoofd, de oogen mede in en steekt haar zakdoek in haar mof. De kerk uitgaande groet zij hare kenissen doch niemand kent haar, zij was een negerin gelijk, toornig gaat zij naar hare familie doch niemand kent haar, zij treedt voor de spiegel en schrikt zelf voor haar zwart gelaat, zij had haar zakdoek in den inkt gedoopt, en had zich geheel zwart gemaakt.

De jeugdige pretmakers waren voor de deur van de kerk blijven wachten, en hadden de dame stikkende van het lagchen thuis gebracht. De namen van de snaken zijn onbekend en zullen wel onbekend blijven.

Sluisch Weekblad, 24 mrt 1876

A Comical Incident. In Amsterdam, a group of mischievous youths played a prank by pouring a bottle of ink into one holy water font and several bottles of Eau d'Anvers (a fragrant perfume) into another at the entrance of a church. As the bell rang for mass, people entering through the right-side door dipped their fingers into the wonderfully scented water, marveling at the delightful aroma of what they believed to be holy water. Meanwhile, those entering through the left-side door dipped their fingers into the ink. Since the church was shrouded in darkness, they didn't notice that their foreheads had been marked with two or three ink smudges as they made the sign of the cross. An elderly lady, particularly enchanted by the scent of the "holy water," dipped her handkerchief into the font. However, instead of leaving through the right-side door, she mistakenly exited through the left-side door. She wiped her forehead and eyes with her handkerchief, then tucked it into her muff. As she left the church, she greeted her acquaintances, but no one recognized her. Her face had turned completely black, resembling that of a "negress." Angrily, she returned home, where even her own family failed to recognize her. Only when she stood before a mirror did she realize, to her horror, that she had blackened her entire face with ink. The mischievous youths had remained near the church entrance, laughing hysterically as they followed her home. The names of the pranksters remain unknown and likely will never be revealed.

[...] 19.30 Tante Frieda. Duitse speelfilm uit 1965 met Elisabeth Flickenschildt, Hansi Kraus, Kathe Braun en anderen. Ludwig zit vol kattenkwaad. Hij wordt van school gestuurd en thuis is iedereen druk bezig met het huwelijk van zijn zuster Annchen. Ook die wil hij een poets bakken en stopt inkt in het wijwater. Tante Frieda, de angst van de familie, is het volgende slachtoffer, maar uiteindelijk behoedt deze tante Frieda hem voor een verblijf in een opvoedingsgesticht.

Limburgsch Dagblad, 8 juni 1976

19:30 Aunt Frieda. A German feature film from 1965 starring Elisabeth Flickenschildt, Hansi Kraus, Käthe Braun, and others. Ludwig is full of mischief. He gets expelled from school, and at home, everyone is busy preparing for the wedding of his sister Annchen. Ludwig decides to play a prank on her

as well, putting ink into the holy water. Aunt Frieda, the terror of the family, becomes his next target. However, in the end, it is Aunt Frieda who prevents Ludwig from being sent to a reformatory school.

[In the eighties and nineties, Hans Janmaat was the leader of the far-right political parties Centrumpartij and Centrum Democraten.]

Maurice Wilbrink en Paul Koopman, *De Wraak van Centrum Democraten-leider Hans Janmaat*

Hans Janmaat werd in de crisisjaren dertig geboren en groeide op in Gouda als oudste zoon van een katholiek gezin dat uiteindelijk negen kinderen zou tellen. Uit wat er over zijn jeugd bekend is; wordt niet duidelijk dat hier een autoritaire persoonlijkheid werd gevormd. Tijdens de oorlog was hij eens een dagje lid van het jeugdverzet en strooide spijkers op de weg, als pesterig misdienaar wierp hij inkt in het wijwater zodat de gelovigen inkt op hun kleding kregen. Obstinaat was hij ook, Hansje at ooit twee dagen niet omdat hij ergens zijn zin niet voor kreeg.

Nieuwsblad van het Noorden, 8 nov. 1994

Maurice Wilbrink and Paul Koopman, The Revenge of Centrum Democraten Leader Hans Janmaat
Hans Janmaat was born during the crisis years of the 1930s and grew up in Gouda as the eldest son of a Catholic family that would eventually have nine children. From what is known about his youth, it is not clear that an authoritarian personality was formed during this time. During the war, he was, for one day, a member of the youth resistance and scattered nails on the road. As a mischievous altar boy, he threw ink into the holy water, causing the faithful to get ink stains on their clothes. He was also stubborn. Young Hans once went two days without eating because he didn't get his way about something.

Appendix 2: Thieves Drink Ink

Huntingdon, Bedford & Peterborough Gazette - Saturday 21
November 1829

< Page 4 of

Image © Reach PLC. Image created courtesy of THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD.

are extracts :—
has commenced in
issued for the 6th,
lar Horse being dis-
d a donation, equal
en.
nd Orissa provincial
e disbanded on the
also extensive.
nance has been re-
Commissary.
Engineer has been
y General has been
ymaster and Marine
hed.
siderably reduced ;
ay Marine have re-
on having gone to

for the present, from any further comments on
the subject.—*Cork Southern Reporter.*

The parties implicated in the robbery at the house of the Rev. W. F. Hook, of Coventry, have been discovered by means of a singular circumstance. It appears that the thieves in their search fell in with a **bottle** of **ink** which it is supposed they mistook for port wine, as there was some left in the glass on the table. Mr. Hook suggested to the magistrates that this might be the means of discovering the burglars, by some of them having marks of **ink** about their clothes. It happened a few days after, that Gardner, the constable, took a young man to the police-office, who was reeling about the streets in a state of intoxication, and upon examining his clothes marks of **ink** were found upon them. He has undergone examination, and has confessed the particulars of the robbery and the number of his accomplices. Two others are in custody.—*Birmingham Gaz.*

The *Album de la Creuse* relates that on the eve of All Saint's Day, a man stopped at a petty inn at Fro-

covered, consequently
2s lower than we report
samples ; and even at
very anxious to purchas
is no alteration from la
quence of the large sup
have received, this grain
decline must be submit
remains at 55s to 60s per
of grain the prices are a
a good demand for bou
market.

CURRENT PR
Per Winchester me
ENGLISH. s.
Old Wheat ... 65 a
New Red Wheat 46 a
New White ditto 54 a
Rye ... 30 a
Barley ... 32 a
Pale Malt ... 56 a
Feed Oats ... 16 a
Brew, or Poland 23 a
Potato ditto 27 a

Newcastle Guardian and Tyne Mercury - Saturday 07
January 1854

< Page 3 of 8 >

Image © THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD. ALL RIGHTS RESERVED.

parently
e
er-
ause
re
cont-
er
ny
o-
profess.
t rather
under-
hen we
T.
as pro-
purpose
of Lords
sons as-
ing the

a stone mason, and about eight o'clock on the **night** of the 15th December was standing in Canada-street, when the prisoner, with another man, named Francis Horn, came up to me and asked me to go and drink with them in the General Wolfe public-house, Shieldfield. We sat in the tap-room. I had some talk with the prisoner about some robberies which he boasted that he had committed. He said he went through the fields to Mr Naters's brewery, broke in, and got some copper, brass, pigeons, some **ink**, and a **bottle** of **brandy**. He said he thought at first that the **bottle** of **ink** was **brandy**, but on raising it to his mouth, in coming away from the counting house, he found it was **ink** and threw it into the fields.—By the JUDGE: I had not known the prisoner any length of time. Was never in his company before. He said he had committed many robberies. The **morning** after we left there was a robbery committed in the Gen. Wolfe, and the police afterwards came to me to ask about the company I was with in the public-house the preceding **night**. When I told them of the statements of prisoner I was immediately afterwards discharged.—The witness

mercy.
recom
been er
by Mes
of his n
week t
ROBI
stealing
James
last.—S
in solit
ELIZ
on the
weight
stated
at Nor
o'clock
a piece
Prosec
the res
Where am
PORK, a

Appendix C: Death by Ink

CAPTAIN JOHN BLAKE to his wife, ———.

1651[-2], February 18. Gambia.—I have been very sick but now am better. Goodman Bourton is dead, he took and drank out of a bottle of **ink** in the night instead of a bottle of water and so was poisoned. This is a bad place. It is miserable hot all day and so little wind that we are almost roasted. Remember my duty to our mother Coborne and to my brother James, and Sister, and to our brother George. *Addressed to John Blake in "Redresse." Signet.*

Cheltenham Looker-On - Saturday 13 November 1897

< Page 8 of 24 ▾ >

Image © Reach PLC. Image created courtesy of THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD.

The Manuscripts of His Grace the Duke of Portland: Preserved at Welbeck Abbey

by Great Britain Royal Commission on Historical Manuscripts, William John Arthur Charles James Cavendish-Bentinck Portland, John Nelson , Robert Harley Oxford , William Stratford , Richard Ward, James Joel Cartwright

Publication date	1893
Publisher	For H. M. Stationery off., by Eyre andSpottiswoode
Collection	americana
Book from the collections of	Harvard University
Language	English
Volume	2
Item Size	856248509

Image © THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD. ALL RIGHTS RESERVED.

ceased, who was 78 years of age, passage of her house on Tuesday her head frightfully smashed. The was to the effect that near the rookery in a smashed condition, air upon the pieces were found. ceased, head was saturated by is stated to have complained of its and notidiness of his mother, red alone. At twenty minutes esday morning he told a witness rolled with his mother the pre- ked her down and killed her, and he added "I killed her with one wed blood on his knuckles. He elf up to the police. There on the prisoner's bedding, and it the crime he went to bed. De- not been occupied. The doctor t violence had been used, and inflicted. The bones of the head ashed into little pieces. The jury ict of wilful murder against old.

**NDON BUILDING SOCIETY
SUSPENDED.**

were as rough as ever. They failed, however, for a second attack, but were finally repulsed.

SAD DEATH OF A BELFAST MERCHANT.

LIVERPOOL, WEDNESDAY.—To-day a winebroker named Francis Quinn, aged about sixty years, died in the Main Bridewell, Liverpool, under extraordinary circumstances. For some time past deceased, it is stated, has been drinking rather heavily, and the previous day he was found by his clerk in his office in a sad plight. His mouth, beard, and collar were covered with some black fluid, and it was afterwards discovered that a bottle of ink had got mixed up with the sample bottles of wines and spirits, and it is believed that Quinn had partaken of the writing fluid in mistake for wine or spirits. He was removed by a police officer to the Northern Hospital, where it was found that he was only suffering from the effects of drink. He was subsequently locked up, and early yesterday morning he complained of feeling cold, and asked for some wine or spirits. An extra rug was supplied, but about 3.40 one of the officials found that he was dead. Deceased's home is at 5, Clarendon-place, May-street, Belfast, and his office was in Revenue Chambers, Liverpool.

(Hear, hear.) If he show into human nature amoc people, there could be no do for comment in the peculiar neighbours. (Applause.)

Father Doherty, in put Mr. Maxwell on behalf of esting lecture. He was gla tendance that night, and b lude to many such instruct ing.

The vote was passed by Maxwell suitably replying.

Father Doherty then an well had consented to deliv convenient date. The st with applause, and the pro

IRISH NATIONAL

GREENCASTLE BRAN

A special meeting of t branch was held in the January 21st, 1894. The enthusiastic, the hall being modate one half of the anxious to take part in the motion of Mr. Hugh Kee

Appendix D: The Blotting Paper Joke

1873: A baby...

‘A baby...’, *The American Republican* [West Chester, Pennsylvania] 1 April 1873 p 1 [CW]

‘Sydney Smith’s Last Joke’, *Morning Press* (10 Apr 1874), 2 [BTB]

1881: One night...

Fifeshire Advertiser - Saturday 21 May 1881

Page 6 of 8

Image © THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD. ALL RIGHTS RESERVED.

8 A.M., and 6 P.M.
Deliveries—
8.30 A.M., and 6.30 P.M.

GLASGOW
ROYAL
do

“COLU

From Bridge V
And from Green
Conveying Pass

Official Guide[B
See Bill (with
from Mr JOE
Advertiser Off
Chemist, Pathbr
DAVID MACBRA

f some of the business the present condition of
did not see that
proper discussion
rule— The resolutions
withdrawn. Mr H. H.
to increase in the ex-
rose to reply, when, at
the house was counted

ESDAY.

mons, Dr Cameron, in a
cond reading of the Free
which he said was ap-
unanimity north of the
to enable parents who
ool fees to apply to the
the Parochial Boards, to
it, thus preserving them

One night the late Colonel Oliphant of Rossie, as he lay in bed, awoke very thirsty, rose for a draught to quench his thirst, and mistaking in the dark a bottle of ink for a bottle of beer, he quaffed the bottle to the bottom. No bad effect followed as to the worthy colonel's health, but it had a noteworthy result, which a lady had philosophy enough to trace. The lady, having related the story of the ink-drinking, was asked, 'What became of the ink?—what happened?' She answered, 'As for the ink, I am not aware that any more was seen of it; and as for the consequences of drinking it, I have heard nothing save that the son, afterwards born to the ink-drinker, became a Writer to the Signet!'

‘One night...’, *Fifeshire Advertiser* (21 May 1881), 6 [SY]

1940: Remedy

● REMEDY

The absent-minded executive walked into his office one morning, nursing a terrific hangover. He turned to his secretary.

“Miss Freyer,” he ordered. “Get me an aspirin and a glass of water.”

The secretary found the aspirin and then filled a glass with water. She handed both to the executive, who swallowed the aspirin quickly. He reached for the water, but his hand found a bottle of ink instead—and he polished that off in short order.

The young lady turned white.

“Good Heavens, Mr. Gillimp!” she gasped. “You drank the bottle of ink by mistake!”

The executive pounded the desk.

“Well, stop standing there with your mouth open!” he shouted. “Find a blotter!” . . .

* * *

'Remedy', *The Akron Beacon Journal* (16 Jun 1940), 86 [BTB]

CLARA MORRIS, whose financial troubles have made her ill (but her illness is not serious), has a number of good stage anecdotes that she proposes to put in her new book.

One of these relates to Edwin Booth. Booth, according to Miss Morris, lay ill in Louisville of a fever, and his medicine was in a black bottle.

During the night, his nurse, by inadvertence, mistook an ink bottle for the medicine vial, and gave Mr. Booth a teaspoonful of ink. He spluttered and coughed over the strange, sweet taste, and the error was discovered. Then the nurse was much worried. She did not know what to do. But Booth said, with a calm smile:

"I'll fix it all right. Just get me a bit of blotting paper to swallow."

'Clara Morris...', *Times Herald* (11 Jan 1903), 35 [BTB]

1957: Mrs...

‘Mrs Carroll Channer...’, *Monroe Booster* (1 May 1957), 4 [BTB]

De beroemde tooneelspeler Matthews gaf schertsend den geest. Zijn bediende, geheel verslagen door de teekenen van den doodstrijd, deed bij vergis zijn heer een lepel inkt in plaats van medicijn innemen. Een der omslaande vrienden bemerkte dit en kon zijne verontwaardiging tegen den bediende niet inhouden. Maar de zieltoogende stamelde : ‘t Is niets, ik zal een stukje vloeipapier inslikken’, wendde ’t hoofd om en stierf.

Drentsche courant, 05-08-1845

The Famous Actor Matthews' Final Jest. The renowned actor Matthews passed away with a jest. His servant, overcome with despair at the signs of his master's death throes, accidentally gave him a spoonful of ink instead of medicine. One of the friends present noticed the mistake and could not contain his indignation towards the servant. However, the dying man feebly murmured: 'It's nothing; I'll swallow a piece of blotting paper,' turned his head, and died.

Appendix E: Some Other Mix Ups

1869

A crusty old bachelor, not liking the way his landlady's daughter had of appropriating his hair oil, filled his bottle with liquid glue the day before a ball, to which she was going. She staid at home in consequence.

Grey River Argus, 22 April 1869: p. 2 [CW]

2001

Sydney Morning Herald [Australia], 14 Sept 2001, Column 8 [BC]

John Hackett, of Redfern, was moved by the story of the North Balgowlah reader who discovered he had been applying roll-on sunscreen to his armpits (Column 8, Tuesday). A few years back, Mr Hackett was told a similar tale of mistaken deodorant - a friend said he'd begun to feel sick after a period of early mornings and late nights. "He put it down to the fact that he'd been spraying his pits with fly spray." No flies on him ...

2001

Sydney Morning Herald, 17 Sept 2001, Column 8 [BC]

Things that go on in the dark ... First flyspray and sunscreen mistaken for deodorant (Column 8, Tuesday and Friday) and now this anecdote from a Blacktown reader. In the early days of his marriage, as his wife "took over the bathroom area", he wondered why his armpits were sticky and painful. "Then I figured out I'd been using hairspray," he confesses.

2001

Sydney Morning Herald, 19 Sept 2001, Column 8 [BC]

More cases of mistaken identity (Column 8, Monday). When ironing, Colin Hadden, of Emu Plains, picked up a likely looking can and sprayed a shirt liberally with spray starch. 'I wondered why it looked brown, and found that I had used cooking spray,' he says. 'At least the shirt wouldn't have stuck to me.' A Pymble reader once accidentally scrubbed his teeth with shaving cream. And a Cherrybrook reader tells us that, years ago, her 'visually challenged' husband mistook the spray adhesive for deodorant. Ouch.

Another reader let us know about her redhead colleague who arrived at work, looking nicely tanned. The compliments faded, however, as her face darkened dramatically through the morning, ending up a patchy orange. That's when she realised she had slathered tanning lotion on to her face instead of sunscreen. "From then on she was affectionately known as Tandoori Betty."

2015 [CW]:

The ultimate bad hair day: Woman ends up in hospital after 'confusing builder's foam with her hair mousse'

- Mystery woman, believed to be from Eastern Europe, grabbed the wrong can when doing her hair
- She accidentally used expanding builder's foam instead of hair mousse and ended up in hospital
- A picture of her in A&E has been widely shared on social media around the world on Tuesday

By [SARA MALM FOR MAILONLINE](#)

PUBLISHED: 15:50 BST, 29 September 2015 | UPDATED: 18:47 BST, 1 October 2016

2017 [BTB]:

stry

[Share](#)

for a report of a man screaming in the roadway. The man, whose face and bald head were painted red, told deputies that he smoked a lot of marijuana and mistook acrylic paint for a spa mask. Since he did not appear to be a danger to himself or others, deputies warned him about making so much noise, and then left the scene.

[The Philomath Express](#)

Philomath, Oregon • Wed, 31 May 2017

Page A2

CLIPPED BY b_taylorblake • 18 hours ago

Appendix F: Forthcoming Note on Inky Night

Abstract: This article examines motif X524, ‘prostitute watches priest use rose-water,’ introduced by D.P. Rotunda on the basis of a novella by Matteo Bandello. The story involves a monk who inadvertently causes a prostitute to stain herself with ink, leading to her being mistaken for a demon in the morning. The article explores variations of this motif in nineteenth-century Britain and America.

Motif X524, ‘prostitute watches priest use rose-water,’ was introduced by D.P. Rotunda based on a novella (§48) by the sixteenth-century Italian author, Matteo Bandello (1485-1561; Bandello, 1911: III, 294-297; Rotunda, 1942: 213; though Thompson declined to pick it up, 1955-1958).

In the story a monk spends a night together with a prostitute in his cell. At matins the monk washes his face with water and goes to pray. The prostitute believes that her lover is using rose-water and decides she will do likewise. Once he has gone, she washes her face, her neck, her breast and her arms (‘a lavarsi tutto il viso, e bagnarsi benissimo il volto, il collo, il petto e le braccia’, Bandello, 1911, III, 296). Unfortunately, she has used a bottle of ink rather than perfume and is now stained black. She then, innocent of this change, falls back to sleep. When the monk returns, he is horrified to see the ‘devil’ in his bed (blackness has long, of course, in Christianity, been associated with demons, e.g. Rothschild 2019). He runs to confess all to his abbot. A party of monks come to the cell and resolves the mystery.

A similar story can be found in a seventeenth-century English broadside (A New delightful Ballad [1685-1688])

X524 is very possibly to be assimilated to Uther’s northern European tale attested in Russia and among the Finns: 1441A, The Inked Girl. ‘A young woman is brought to an old man to spend the night with him. During the night she smears herself with black ink. The next morning, when the man sees the black face beside him, he thinks he has slept with the devil’ (II, 222). All depends on whether the smearing is deliberate or not (more of which below). There are also, note, some British stories of lecherous types waking up with the ‘devil’, but these involve choices on the part of the woman. For instance, one seventeenth-century broadside has a woman who wears a mask in bed to convince her bed-partner that she is a demon (The BITER BITTEN, 1685-1688?).

Rotunda did not give a workable name to X524. The story could better have been described as ‘Sleeper (briefly awaking) accidentally rubs ink on their body leading to misinterpretation in the morning.’ It is not elegant, but it takes in more modern versions of this belief legend, versions which have escaped folklorists’ notice.

From the 1870s the Anglophone press ran numerous X524 stories as belief legends in their columns. I’ve put in a pdf source book about thirty examples (Young, 2024: c. 8000

words). This small report from 1872 is one of the earliest unambiguous examples known to me.

A Mt. Morris girl who had the tooth ache, made a mistake in the applying a remedy in the night, and got hold of a bottle of purple ink instead of liniment. The inside of her mouth, teeth, and blooming cheeks were found of a peculiar color in the morning, much to the alarm of the lady and her friends. They were relieved to find it only a mortifying mistake and not a mortifying face ('A Mt. Morris girl').

There are many variants (see Young 2024). Invariably the confusion comes about because of the dark: but there are instances where panic or drunkenness explain the mistake. The person sometimes puts the ink on themselves: but there are reports where a wife puts ink on her husband (this may even be the dominant type in the United States). Typically, the ink is believed to be a medicine of some description (liniment etc): but there are also cases where it is believed to be holy water or alcohol. Overwhelmingly, the ink is rubbed on. But there are three instances where the ink is swallowed (Arnold, 1859: 97; 'Railway Yarns', 1902; 'The man...', 1902). Then there is one case where the 'ink' is not actually ink: a woman powders her face in the dark with tooth powder ('A Young Woman's', 1908). The act of drinking or rubbing is accidental. This is the motor of the story.

Most interesting is the question of misinterpretation in the morning. In one case – a short story set in the Raj – a drunk who had accidentally swallowed and spilt red ink all over himself is believed to have been murdered ('Railway Yarns', 1902). He is hungover. In some cases, there is initially concern about the health of the person: see the example quoted above, with the girl's mortified face ('A Mt. Morris girl', 1872). One man who has put ink on his face instead of cologne is believed to be insane ('The friends...' 1899). The most interesting stories, in relation to *Bandello*, are the handful in which the husband is believed to have changed ethnicity overnight: e.g. 'she was horrified to see a black man lying by the side of her' ('The Latest Yarn', 1879).

Here the concerns are not, as in *Bandello*, supernatural, they are racial: pointing to well-known anxieties in nineteenth-century American and European societies. The story can, though, also be easily adapted to other anxieties. Certain, as noted above, involve holy water and the narrator offers a decidedly anti-Catholic take (e.g. 'Pastor' 1899 – a sermon). There are also two stories that stress the ability of the human mind to heal through belief: the sufferer took the ink and felt better ('Annual Meeting', 1899; 'Cured by Faith', 1902; placebo and nocebo were the inspiration for several nineteenth-century belief legends, Young, 2022: 426-27).

No nineteenth-century English-language version (known to me) is sexual. Here there are two possibilities. The first is that the story had evolved away from sex by the time these new versions began to be published in the 1870s. The second is that there were sexual stories in oral circulation, but that it was not possible, for reasons of public sensibilities,

to publish them as news or fiction in the mid or late 1800s. I have looked elsewhere at this issue of the (apparent) invisibility of erotic belief legends in a Victorian milieu (Young, 2022: 89-90, 145-146, 148-151, 174-178, 184-187). The existence of sexual French and Polish nineteenth-century versions makes me think that the latter is more likely (Du Gast de Bois-Saint-Just, 1809: I, 292-293; Kolor, 1887)

As noted above there is a pdf source file of versions of what I call 'Inky Night' (Young 2024). I am using this legend as a test case to see whether it is credible and useful to publish all sources for a given legend type and share publicly. The file can easily be updated. If, then, any readers can contribute other versions in any language I would be very grateful to receive them!

I acknowledge the interest of parallel cases like, for instance, the man who sprays his underarms with paint instead of deodorant. But I will restrict myself, at least for the moment to ink (or similar substances) put on accidentally in the dark that change appearances, with incredulity or misinterpretation in the morning.

Acknowledgements: Chris Woodyard rediscovered this belief legend and Bonny Taylor-Blake and Brian Chapman found most examples. Rainer Wehse supplied the English broadside reference. Peter Burger sent in an impressive group of similar Dutch nineteenth-century news-reports and Filip Graliński a crucial Polish text. I am grateful to all six!

Bibliography to be included only in the published version.

Appendix G: Ink Miscellany

Norwood News - Saturday 24 June 1876

Page 6 of 8

Image © Reach PLC. Image created courtesy of THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD.

IC QUESTION.

...delivered at the day...
 ...no doubt, to the vaile...
 ...the attendance was ounc...
 ...for the lecture as but...
 ...the close the are v...
 ...on the whole, a present. J. W. Flower, to take the chair, but was e opening of the lecture. ll filled by Mr. Inchbald. ened with prayer, few observations in in- arking that the Saviour after days there should be e doctrines. He asked if day, and alluded to the ion, which people were omanists and Ritualists, position

WHAT THE "WORLD" SAYS.
 (Notes by "Atlas.")

I have heard, but can hardly believe, that after next month Government intends putting restrictions in the way of volunteers resigning and leaving their corps so easily as at present. If this is true, what a stampede there will be!

I hear, with much regret, that Mr. Ashton Dilke's state of health is such as to occasion serious concern to his friends.

I hear a curious story from the academic groves of Dublin. An examination has just been held at Trinity College for one of the higher prizes. The struggle virtually lay between two candidates, and the ultimate test was the production of an essay upon political economy. The candidates, being seated in a room with the examiners, and having pens and paper placed before them for the purpose of producing their essays, had proceeded for some time, when one of the two candidates observed that his most dangerous rival, while sitting

Norwood News - Saturday 24 June 1876

Page 6 of 8

Image © Reach PLC. Image created courtesy of THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD.

...position.
 ...was well received, said it ad brought them together, ended the discharge of an to be shirked. A perilous ong the perils of the day at the Established Church with the very worst prin- proof of this the lecturer aalistic journals passages v openly promulgated, and s really worse than Ro- ed people as to its real at shoals of the laity and ing towards Rome. That t be gainsaid. The Ritu- athy with the Bible. He s in correspondence with a he free circulation of the . calculated to do immense ears after writing that, the gone over to the Church of doctrine of baptismal ret- ts, he said Mr. Bennett, of oment a child was baptised hrist, a child of God, and m of heaven." Between he Church of Rome there

...served that his most dangerous rival, while sitting at the table, was frequently absorbed in thought, and appeared to find that the position most advantageous to mental exerci as to lean back in his chair, and fix his eyes upon his knees under the table. The sus- picious of Mr. A. being excited, he accidentally dropped his pen, and, stooping to pick it up, saw on the knees of Mr. B. a book, which he recognised as a volume of Mr. Stuart Mill's Essays. With great presence of mind he wrote on a slip of paper a message to the following effect: "I see your book. I will say nothing about it if you will quietly withdraw from the competition." Mr. B. wrote back an answer, saying that he "did not know what this might mean"; whereupon Mr. A., rising solemnly, denounced to the examiners the conduct of Mr. B. in respect of the possession of the book. The examiners asking for an explanation, Mr. B. rose, and was indignantly denying the charge, when he fell prone on his face. At first it was thought that a fate similar to that of Ananias had befallen him; but upon one of the examiners, in the hurry of the moment, splashing the contents of a bottle of ink in his face, it was made clear that he was only in a fainting- fit, and presently he recovered. The matter has excited a profound sensation throughout the college, and is now I believe, in course of investigation.

It is likely that the Empress Eugénie will shortly

Image © Reach PLC. Image created courtesy of THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD.

AT MOMENT.

... day Lord
and M. Huntley Car-
open remaining
the of King
en. I will be surely
great moments of his-
living ds break the
thousands of years ago
eyes look in on the long
of the dead. If the
King is found within
fact that almost dwarfs
only shall we yearn to
dry his lips could un-
this earth has suffered
plished since he passed
nshine of an Egyptian
g and an autocrat, to
and darkness wherein
eps! He could tell us
us story, but none so
varied as that which
hear from us. To him
s of Homer, Christ,
Caesar, Dante, Shakes-
Napoleon would convey
The civilisations of
ome, Spain, Portugal,

BY BERNARD JEFFS, F.R.G.S.

THE world goes by slowly in Andalusia: hardly a breath of air stirs the palms or ripples the Guadalquivir as it creeps between its muddy banks. Lizards bask in the scorching heat of the mid-day sun; beetles creep lazily among the cactus roots; multi-coloured butterflies flit among the olive and orange groves. To this land comes the idler and the dreamer. It is here that he may throw aside the cant and convention of modern civilisation and bathe in an atmosphere of freedom and romance. To-day, as in the days when turbaned sheiks wandered through the narrow streets, the air is heavy with the scent of the odorous orange blossom, and the faint perfumes of roses.

Approaching Seville from the north the journey is monotonous and uninteresting. For hours the train crawls along the cactus-lined track, bordered on either side by olive and orange groves. Great stretches of sandy waste, relieved here and there by patches of rock, add to the monotone of the landscape and present to the eye the aspect of a land similar in many respects to Palestine and the Near East. The country seems to have sunk into an eternal "siesta," during which the dust of ages has accumulated, never again to depart.

AS EVENING CLOSES.

"Fate has buried here
A rich possession, but still greater
promise"

THUS wrote Grillparzer in his epitaph on the most spontaneous, and possibly the most careless of composers, Franz Peter Schubert, who was born on 31 January, just a hundred and twenty-six years ago.

Many of Schubert's greatest compositions were written in an almost incredibly short space of time, and the ineritable results of such industry are apparent in many of his works, and especially so to the serious student. He was only eighteen when he wrote "The Erl-King," one of his best known songs. The setting was completed in a single day, and Goethe, the author of the poem, expressed dissatisfaction with it, although the mere fact that it is now ranked as one of the most dramatic songs ever written seems to show that Goethe's taste was at fault.

EASY COME, EASY GO.

It was in the middle of the night that he was inspired to write "Die Forelle" and he hastened out of bed to commit it to paper. When it was finished he reached for the bottle of pounce (sand) to dry the manuscript, but he was so tired, tradition has it, that he picked up the ink bottle instead and poured it over the sheets, spoiling the greater part of the score. "Hark, Hark, the Lark" was composed under peculiar circumstances. Subject with a few boon companions

promoted by the experience of a similar body, and have made plans for the future which should result in their immunity from any like occurrence. As a result of the defalcations of an official, the Norfolk County Council lost the huge sum of £50,000, and, while casting not the slightest aspersion on their own employees, of high or low degree, the local body decided to appoint a sub-committee to go into the question of the system of financial control and audit of their income and expenditure. The report of this sub-committee, with its recommendations, was adopted by the County Council yesterday, having previously received the approval of the Finance Committee and of the Standing Joint Committee as far as it related to the police service. The recommendations are to come into operation on 1 April.

WIDENING TRENT BRIDGE.

There is much talk in Nottingham at present as to the necessity for another bridge over the Trent, near the existing Trent Bridge, to cut into the Loughborough-road. The proposal is made because the existing bridge—the city practical artery from the city to the south—is insufficient to carry the traffic across at its ordinary flow, and not because the bridge is unsafe. Yesterday a well-known London expert, who is City Engineer, a surveyor and

SIR
Ess
VAG
With
Dodge
and in
the Fe
Monday
(Chanc
Treasu
by the
Eric C
The
aboliti
and t
with
operat
of tax
Sir
192000

the measured tread of the lark as they passed; crushed by the double blow that had come upon him, he heard not even the boom of the morning gun, or the rattle of the drums and the sweet shrill fifes playing the reveille; he had not heard even a row in the adjacent lines, which had actually brought the inlying picket under arms, when some fellow, obnoxious to certain tipsy youngsters of his corps, had resisted being 'drawn,' and fiercely resented a quart bottle of ink being put into his shower-bath, which turned him into a species of Othello, and prevented his appearance on parade till he had been operated upon by the doctor with a lemon.

Feverish alike in mind and body,

b
f
il
l
r
t
a
s
a
c
t
t
e
u
l
l
c
a
u
c

Where am I?

Uxbridge & W. Drayton Gazette - Saturday 11 January
1913

Image © Reach PLC. Image created courtesy of THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD.

Appendix H: Seventeenth-Century Broadside

A New delightful Ballad. Called, / Debauchery Scared: / OR, THE / Beggar wench turn'd into a Devil, / Together with the Pollicy of Bumpkin; / Giving a peasant Account of Commical Passages between a Country Gentle / man, and a London Beggar-wench (London: Printed for J. Bissel at the Bible and Harp, ND [1685-1688])

A Country Gentleman came up to Town,
to taste the delights of the City,
Who had to his Servant a jocular Clown,
accounted to be very witty:
His master one night got drunk as a Rat,
and swore he would turn him away Sir,
Lest he would get him a bit for his Cat,
and into his Chamber convey her.
Some jolly Dame he was willing to have,
and gave to his Bumpkin a Guiney,
Who had the wit not to give it, but save
the far better part of the money;
To find out a Punck, he walkt in the street,
and backwards and forwards kept trudging;
At last a young beggar wench he did meet,
who was in great want of a Lodging:
Sweet-heart (said he) if thoult give thy consent
to go home, and lye with my master,
Ile give thee half a Crown for thy content,
and save thee from any disaster:
It being late, she fearing the watch,
Besides it was very cold weather;
[So] that they quickly both made up the match,
and trudgd to his master together.

Bumpkin was arch, as he homewards did come
he gave her a bout by the way sir;
Then to his master he carried her home,
who in a dark Chamber lay sir:
He bid her be sure let his master not know,
by any means she was a mumper,
But bid her to rise before day-light, and go,
or Ad-swounds he would heartily thump her.
Bumpkin his Trull to the Chamber he led,
and then to his Bed took his way sir,
She quickly undrest, and gropt into the Bed,
and close to the Gentleman lay sir,
Eager of Joy, he gave her a Kiss,
and hugd her with flaming desire: The Gentleman swore that she smelld so of Cheese
he could not indure to lye by her.
He bid her get up to a place in the room,
where a Bottle stood of Rose-water,
And wash her Face to take away the fume,
then come into Bed again after;
A Bottle of Ink there happend to stand,
and for the Rose-water she took it,
Pouring a spoonful out into her hand,
and over her face she did stroak it.
Then to their Joys they eagerly fell,
till at last it began to be Light sir,
Then looking he thought her the Devil of Hell,
and ran out of Bed in a fright sir;
Crying, the Devil, the Devil was there,

she being affrighted ran after,
In a tattered old smock, crying where is he where
which put all the street in a laughter.

Appendix I: Dutch Inky Night Cases (from Peter Burger)

Peter submitted this '27 August, 2024' (sorry Peter that this took so long) and wrote 'Main source: Dutch digitized newspapers available through delpher.nl'. Peter stresses that the sources have not been checked for OCR errors. I've added AI translations into English.

ZWARTMAKING DOOR COQUETTERIE.

Mejufvrouw Le Duc, bij welke de Graaf van Clermont, Prins van den bloede, zijn hof maakte, en die men wil dat hij op het einde zijns levens getrouwd hebbe, was nog te bed des morgens ten 11 uren, toen hare kamenier haar ijllings kwam wekken, en de komst van den Prins berigten. — 'Geef mij spoedig,' zeide zij, 'mijn Eau de fleurs d'Orange, dat' op de Schoorsteen staat, en laat de luiken dicht, tot Zijne Hoogheid komt.' Haastig wascht zij zich het gezicht, hals en armen. De glazen worden ontsloten. De Prins deinst met afschrik terug, zoodra hij haar ziet Door een onwillige vergissing, namelijk, had de kamenier een fleschje met inkt voor het andere genomen; en nu oordeele men, in welk eene gedaante deze dame zich aan het oog van haren minnaar vertoonde!

Surinaamsche Courant, 12 April 1838.

Defamation Through Coquetry: Miss Le Duc, with whom the Count of Clermont, a prince of the blood, was courting – and who, it is said, he married at the end of his life – was still in bed at 11 o'clock in the morning when her maid hurriedly came to wake her and announce the arrival of the Prince. 'Quickly give me,' she said, 'my Eau de fleurs d'Orange (Orange Blossom Water) that is on the mantelpiece, and keep the shutters closed until His Highness arrives.' She quickly washed her face, neck, and arms. The shutters were then opened. The Prince recoiled in shock the moment he saw her. Through an unfortunate mistake, the maid had taken a bottle of ink instead of the orange blossom water. Now imagine the appearance this lady presented to the eyes of her suitor!

Mademoiselle Leduc, à qui le comte de Clermont, prince du sang, faisait sa cour, et qu'on croit qu'il a épousée secrètement dans les dernières années de sa vie, était encore au lit à onze heures du matin, quand sa femme - de - chambre l'éveille en sursaut, en lui annonçant que le Prince arrive. 'Donnez-moi vite, dit-elle, mon' eau de fleur d'orange qui est sur la cheminée, et n'ouvrez les fenêtres que quand, son Altesse entrera. Elle se dépêche de se laver le visage, la gorge et les bras: les fenêtres s'ouvrent; le Prince se présente et recule d'effroi en la regardant. Par une méprise involontaire, la femme-de-chambre avait donné une bouteille d'encre, au lieu de celle de fleur d'orange, et l'on juge dans quel état mademoiselle Leduc s'offrait aux yeux de son amant.

Jean-Louis-Marie Du Gast de Bois-Saint-Just (1809), *Paris, Versailles et les provinces, au 18e siècle. Anecdotes sur la vie privée de plusieurs ministres, évêques, magistrats célèbres... et autres personnages connus sous les règnes de Louis XV et Louis XVI*. Volume 1. Paris: Le Normant; Lyon: Yvernault et Cabin.

Mademoiselle Leduc, courted by the Count of Clermont, a prince of the blood—and believed to have secretly married him in the later years of his life—was still in bed at eleven in the morning when her maid suddenly woke her, announcing the Prince's arrival. 'Quickly, give me my orange blossom water from the mantelpiece,' she said, 'and don't open the windows until His Highness enters.' She hastily washed her face, neck, and arms. The windows were then opened, and the Prince entered, only to recoil in horror at the sight of her. Through an unintentional mistake, the maid had handed her a bottle of ink instead of the orange blossom water. One can only imagine the state in which Mademoiselle Leduc appeared before her suitor.

Te St. Omer heeft eene schoone en bevallige jonge Dame, uit vrees voor het onweder, 's nachts een flesch genomen, waarin zij meende dat wijwater was, en daarmede hare meubelen, kleederen en bed besproeid's Morgens bleek het dat zij ongelukkig een flesch met inkt daartoe had gebruikt, en staarde zij met groot leedwezen op al het bedorven goed.

Leydse Courant, 25 Juli 1856

At Saint-Omer. In Saint-Omer, a beautiful and charming young lady, out of fear of the thunderstorm at night, took a bottle that she believed contained holy water and sprinkled it over her furniture, clothes, and bed. In the morning, it turned out that, unfortunately, she had used a bottle of ink for this purpose. She looked with great regret at all the ruined belongings.

Men verhaalt een zonderling avontuur, dat tijdens een onweder in eene kostschool voor jufvrouwen in België heeft plaats gehad. Het weerlichtte en donderde verschrikkelijk; niettemin sliepen de pensionairen zoo als men op vijftienjarigen ouderdom slaapt. Er was enkel eene oude dienstmeid, die in de slaapkamers rondzwierf en gestadig het teeken des kruises maakte. Geen wijwater hebbende, ging zij beneden naar de kast, waar dat gewoonlijk staat, en nam in den donker de flesch, waarvan zij een gedeelte van den inhoud in een potje goot. Vervolgens in de eene hand het wijwater en in de andere hand de palmhei houdende, besproeide zij de jeugdige leerlingen, die aan hare bewaking waren toevertrouwd. Toen dit gedaan en het weder bedaarder geworden was, ging zij op hare beurt slapen. Maar des morgens, toen de kostscholieren wakker werden, was geheel de school in opschudding. In hare overhaasting had de oppaster zich bedrogen en in plaats van de wijwaterflesch had zij de inktflesch genomen; al de pensionairen zagen er gelijk moorinnkens uit.

Provinciale Drentsche en Asser courant, 17 aug 1871

A Strange Adventure at a Boarding School in Belgium. A peculiar incident is recounted that took place during a thunderstorm at a girls' boarding school in Belgium. The lightning and thunder were terrifying, yet the boarders slept as deeply as fifteen-year-olds typically do. Only an old maidservant roamed around the dormitories, constantly making the sign of the cross. Having no holy water at hand, she went downstairs to the cupboard where it was usually kept and, in the dark, took a bottle, pouring part of its contents into a small container. Then, holding the 'holy water' in one hand and the blessed palm in the other, she sprinkled the young pupils entrusted to her care. When the storm subsided, and her task was

complete, she went to bed herself. But the next morning, when the boarders woke up, the entire school was in an uproar. In her haste, the caretaker had made a mistake and, instead of the holy water bottle, had taken the ink bottle. All the boarders looked like little Moors!

De dametjes eener kostschool in Belgie kwamen er beter af dan de Podenzanezen. Het onweer woedde met alle kracht; de eene bliksemstraal joeg den ander en de donder ratelde door 't luchtruim. 't Was nacht en de dametjes sliepen den slaap der jeugd en die is vast. Zij ontwaakten door 't onweer niet. Dat verontrustte eene oude dienstmaagd. Zij bezocht achtereenvolgens de slaapvertrekken en maakte gedurig het teeken des kruises, en om tegen het dreigend gevaar nog zekerder behoedmiddel te hebben, haalde zij de flesch met wijwater en besprenkelde hiermee de slapenden. Eerst nadat het weer bedaard was, begaf zij zich weder ter ruste. 's Morgens bij 't opstaan konden de meisjes zich niet begrijpen, hoe ze er allen zoo zwart gevlekt waren; zij wisten niet, dat ze in den nacht besprenkeld waren geworden met inkt. Maar 't onweer had haar toch geen kwaad gedaan.

Bolswards Nieuwsblad, 24 aug 1871

The Young Ladies of a Belgian Boarding School. The young ladies of a Belgian boarding school fared better than the residents of Podenzana. The thunderstorm raged with full force; lightning bolts followed one another in quick succession, and thunder echoed through the skies. It was night, and the young ladies slept the deep sleep of youth—a sleep that is sound and undisturbed. They did not wake from the storm. However, the tumult alarmed an old maidservant. She visited the dormitories one after the other, continuously making the sign of the cross. To provide an even more secure protection against the looming danger, she fetched the bottle of holy water and sprinkled it over the sleeping girls. Only after the storm had calmed did she retire to bed herself. The next morning, when the girls rose, they were baffled as to how they had all become so speckled with black stains. They did not realize that during the night, they had been sprinkled with ink instead of holy water. Still, the storm had done them no harm.

Den noodlottige zegen.

Op zeker dorp, dicht bij Lublin, woonde een oude geestelijke, die voor zeer vermogend werd gehouden. Voor eenige maanden kwamen in het nachtelijk uur roovers bij hem binnendringen, die geld verlangden. 'Wij willen de Turken gaan bestrijden,' zeiden zij 'en om oorlog te voeren heeft men geld nodig.'

'Gij doet daar zeer wel aan,' gaf de geestelijke ten antwoord. 'Trekt gij werkelijk ten strijde, dan wil ik u gaarne helpen, en niet alleen met geld, maar ook met mijn zegen.'

Bij deze woorden begaf hij zich in een zijvertrek, kwam met 800 roebels terug en overhandigde deze den roovers. Tegelijkertijd besprenkelde hij hen met wijwater.

Het gansche voorval was in het duister afgespeeld.

Niet zoo gauw waren de roovers weg, of de geestelijke wekte zijne dienstbode en liet alarm luiden.

In een oogwenk waren alle dorpsbewoners op de been. De geestelijke vertelde hun het voorgevallene, verzocht hun de roovers na te zetten en besloot met te zeggen: «Gij kunt hen gemakkelijk herkennen, want het wijwater, waarmede ik hen besprenkelde was inkt.»

Men begon dadelijk de roovers te vervolgen en had ze ook weldra ingehaald, want zij hadden rustig hun weg vervolgd en waren niet weinig ontsteld, toen zij bemerkten dat zij er als Mooren uitzagen.

The Ill-Fated Blessing. In a village near Lublin, there lived an old clergyman who was believed to be quite wealthy. Some months ago, late at night, robbers broke into his home, demanding money. 'We want to fight against the Turks,' they said, 'and to wage war, one needs money.' 'You are doing very well with that cause,' the clergyman replied. 'If you are truly going to battle, I am happy to help you, not only with money but also with my blessing.' With these words, he went into an adjoining room, returned with 800 rubles, and handed the money to the robbers. At the same time, he sprinkled them with holy water. The entire incident had taken place in darkness. No sooner had the robbers left than the clergyman woke his servant and sounded the alarm. In a flash, all the villagers were up and about. The clergyman recounted the event, asked them to pursue the robbers, and concluded by saying, 'You will recognize them easily, for the holy water with which I sprinkled them was ink.' The villagers immediately set off in pursuit and soon caught up with the robbers, who had calmly continued on their way. They were quite shocked to realize that they now looked like Moors.

[Peter adds here that in another version: 'In the version printed by a Dutch-language newspaper published in the US, *De Volksvriend*, on 14 November 1878, Polish Lublin has been changed into Irish Dublin'.]

Heviger ontroering dan die welke onlangs eene dame te Parijs ondervond, zal zeker zelden den boezem eener echtgenootte doorschokt hebben. Te goeder trouw te zijn gehuwd met een blanke, die op een mooien dag een neger blijkt te zijn. Ziehier het geval: Er woedde dezer dagen een hevige storm boven Parijs, die ook de vreedzame woning van het echtpaar Martins deed schudden op hare grondvesten. Had zulks weinig invloed op den gezonden slaap des heeren Martin, uit den geest zijner echtgenootte woei de storm alle slaperigheid ver weg. Zij was telkens beducht dat het huis zou instorten.

Maar nog vreeselijker uitwerking scheen de storm te hebben gehad, naar zij bij het aanbreken van den dag bemerkte. Het gezicht van haar man was in één nacht pikzwart geworden!

In de grootste ontsteltenis werden de bureu geroepen om het treurige en wonderbaarlijke feit te constateeren; de heer Martin zag er uit alsof zijn gezicht zorgvuldig met lampzwart was ingesmeerd. Niemand wist eene verklaring te geven, tot het eindelijk uitkwam: Mevr. Martin, die bonne Catholique maar tevens niet bijster heldhaftig was, had in den angst van den stormachtigen nacht eene flesch wijwater (?) genomen en den inhoud daarvan over het gelaat van haar echtvriend gegoten om deze

voor mogelijke gevaren te behoeden. Deze inhoud bleek bij onderzoek niets anders te zijn dan inkt. De verhaler van dit bericht deelt niet mede hoe het kwam dat de heer Martin onder dit stortbad niet ontwaakte. (Hdbl.)

De Zeeuw, 1 sep 1892

A Parisian Lady's Shock. A more intense shock than the one recently experienced by a lady in Paris has likely seldom shaken the heart of a wife. To marry in good faith a white man, only for him to appear as a Black man one day. Here is the story: A violent storm recently raged over Paris, shaking even the peaceful home of the Martins to its very foundations. While this had little effect on the sound sleep of Mr. Martin, the storm completely banished any sleepiness from the mind of his wife. She feared constantly that the house might collapse. But the storm seemed to have had an even more dreadful effect, as she discovered at daybreak. Her husband's face had turned pitch-black overnight! In her utmost shock, the neighbors were summoned to witness the tragic and bizarre phenomenon: Mr. Martin's face looked as though it had been carefully smeared with soot. No one could explain the cause of this transformation—until the truth finally came out. Mrs. Martin, a devout Catholic but not especially brave, had, in the terror of the stormy night, grabbed a bottle of what she believed to be holy water (?) and poured its contents over her husband's face to protect him from potential dangers. Upon inspection, however, the contents of the bottle turned out to be ink. The narrator of this report does not explain how Mr. Martin managed to sleep through this deluge.

Als 't maar helpt!

Een landeigenaar nabij Landeshut, in Silezië, kreeg 's nachts zulk een hevige kiespijn, dat hij niet slapen kon. Door zijn gesteun werd ook zijn vrouw wakker, die hem den raad gaf, zich het gelaat in te wrijven met kamferspiritus die in een flesch op de vensterbank stond. De man deed het en sliep spoedig in. Toen de vrouw den volgenden morgen bij het ontwaken naar haar echtgenoot keek, begon zij angstig te schreeuwen, want naast naar lag niet haar man, maar een ... neger. Wakker geworden door het gegil, vroeg deze in goed Duitsch wat er aan de hand was, en nu bleek spoedig, dat de kiespijnlijder 's nachts in plaats van de flesch met kamferspiritus, een flesch met inkt in handen gekregen had, Alleen door suggestie was de man dus van zijn pijn genezen.

Sumatra Post, 5 April 1911

As Long as It Works! A landowner near Landeshut, in Silesia, suffered from such severe toothache one night that he couldn't sleep. His groaning woke his wife, who advised him to rub his face with camphor spirit, which was in a bottle on the windowsill. The man did as instructed and soon fell asleep. The next morning, when the wife woke up and looked at her husband, she began screaming in terror. Next to her was not her husband, but a... Black man. Awoken by her cries, the man asked in perfect German what was wrong. It quickly became apparent that during the night, the toothache sufferer had grabbed a bottle of ink instead of the bottle of camphor spirit. It turned out that the man's pain had been relieved purely by suggestion.

Een reisavontuur. — De volgende geschiedenis wordt onder voorwaarde van stipte geheimhouding medegedeeld. Een ziekelijk heer en diens vrouw hadden een bed genomen in een slaapwagen van een spoortrein; tegen middernacht ontwaakte de zieke onder hevige pijn in den rug en verzocht hij zijne vrouw om hem spoedig een mosterdpleister gereed te maken. De dame doet wat haar gevraagd is en loopt daarna naar het andere eind van den wagen, om de pleister bij 't lamplicht te verwarmen, opdat zij goed zal trekken. Op den terugweg naar den zieken echtgenoot komt de kleine vrouw ongelukkig bij het verkeerde bed, waarin een dikke wijnhandelaar rust. Snel schuift zij de gordijnen weg, slaat de dekens op en flap! de pleister zit op den rug van den reiziger. Op hetzelfde oogenblik roept de zieke uit zijn kooi: 'Maar Marie, waar blijft gij dan toch?' Nu eerst bemerkte de arme vrouw hare vreeselijkste vergissing; in een paar stappen is zij bij het bed van haren echtgenoot en fluistert hem het ongeval in 't oor. Ondanks zijn pijn barst deze in een schaterlach uit en lacht zoodanig, tot dat hij zijn pijn vergeten heeft. Het is een oogenblik doodstil; daar hoort men in het bed van den wijnhandelaar luidde vloeken en smartkreten: Menschen help mij! wat zit daar op mijn rug? De hemel zij mij genadig! O! wat brandt dat! Water! Vuur! Au! O wee! mijn rug! Het bed brand I Hemel en aarde! Breng water! Mijn rug! enz. enz. Met den sluier der naastenliefde omhullen wij het verder verloop van de geschiedenis.

Hoornsche Courant, 20 aug. 1884

A Travel Adventure. The following story is shared under the condition of strict confidentiality. A sickly gentleman and his wife had taken a berth in the sleeping car of a train. Around midnight, the ailing man awoke with severe back pain and asked his wife to quickly prepare a mustard plaster for him. The lady did as he asked and walked to the other end of the car to warm the plaster near the lamp, so it would work effectively. On her way back to her husband, however, the petite woman accidentally approached the wrong bed, where a stout wine merchant was sleeping. Without realizing her mistake, she swiftly drew back the curtains, pulled up the blankets, and flap! the plaster was placed on the traveler's back. At the same moment, the sick man called out from his berth: 'But Marie, where are you?' Only then did the poor woman realize her dreadful mistake. In just a few steps, she reached her husband's bed and whispered the accident in his ear. Despite his pain, the man burst into laughter, laughing so hard that he forgot about his discomfort entirely. For a brief moment, there was complete silence. Then, from the wine merchant's bed, loud curses and cries of pain erupted: 'Help me, someone! What is on my back? Heaven have mercy on me! Oh, it burns! Water! Fire! Ow! My back! The bed is on fire! Heaven and earth, bring water! My back!' And so on. With the veil of charity, we shall leave the further course of this story to the imagination.

De volgende geschiedenis wordt onder voorwaarde van stipte geheimhouding medegedeeld. Een ziekelijk heer en zijn knecht hadden een bed genomen in een slaapwagen van een spoortrein; tegen middernacht ontwaakte de zieke onder hevige pijn in den rug en verzocht hij zijne bediende om hem spoedig een mosterdpleister gereed te maken. De man doet wat hem gevraagd is en loopt daarna naar het andere eind van den wagen, om de pleister bij 't lamplicht te verwarmen, opdat zij goed zal trekken. Op den

terugweg naar den zieken meester komt de knecht ongelukkig bij het verkeerde bed, waarin een dikke makelaar rust, Snel schuift hij de gordijnen weg, slaat de dekens op en flap! de pleister zit op den rug van den reiziger. Op hetzelfde oogenblik roept de zieke uit zijn kooi,,Maar Jan, waar blijft gij dan toch?" Nu eerst bemerkte de arme knecht zijn vreeselyke vergissing; in een paar stappen is hij bij het bed van zyn meester en fluistert hem het ongeval in 't oor. Ondanks zijn pijn barst deze in een schaterlach uit en lacht zoodanig, totdat hij zijn pijn vergeten heeft. Het is een oogenblik doodstil; daar hoort men in het bed van den wijnhandelaar luide zuchten en smartkreten. Met den sluier der naastenliefde omhullen wij het verder verloop van de geschiedenis.

Java-Bode, 27 sep 1884

The Following Story Is Shared Under Strict Confidentiality. A sickly gentleman and his servant had taken a berth in a sleeping car of a train. Around midnight, the ailing man woke up with severe back pain and asked his servant to quickly prepare a mustard plaster. The servant did as instructed and walked to the far end of the car to warm the plaster near the lamp, ensuring it would adhere effectively. On his way back to his master, however, the servant accidentally approached the wrong bed, where a stout broker was soundly asleep. Without realizing his mistake, he quickly drew back the curtains, pulled up the blankets, and—flap!—applied the plaster firmly onto the back of the sleeping traveler. At that very moment, the sick gentleman called out from his berth: ‘But Jan, where are you?’ It was only then that the poor servant realized his dreadful mistake. In just a few steps, he reached his master’s bed and whispered the mishap in his ear. Despite his pain, the gentleman burst into laughter—laughing so heartily that he completely forgot his discomfort. For a brief moment, silence fell over the sleeping car. Then, from the broker’s bed came loud sighs and cries of pain. With the veil of charity, we shall leave the rest of this story to the imagination.

Peter adds: This story has been used as a plot device by Trollope.

Christmas At Thompson Hall, Trollope N.Y., Harper, 1877. Originally published in *The Graphic*, Christmas number, 1876. Later collected in *Why Frau Frohmann Raised Her Prices and Other Stories*, 1882. An English edition with the title: *Thompson Hall*, was published by Sampson Low, 1885.

Mrs. Brown, journeying with her husband from the south of France to her old home in England for the Christmas holidays, spent the night in Paris where Mr. Brown developed a sore throat. Thinking to make a mustard poultice from a pot of mustard she had seen in the salon, Mrs. Brown lost her way on her return and, entering the wrong room, discovered after the poultice had been applied that the patient was not her husband. Traced next morning by the handkerchief she had used, her husband made as satisfactory an explanation as was possible to the aggrieved and blistered Mr. Jones. During the remainder of their journey the Browns found themselves accompanied by

this same gentleman, whom on their arrival they discovered to be the intended husband of Mrs. Brown's sister Jane, who had been invited there to meet them.

© 1948 Princeton University Press, 1976 renewed PUP. Reprinted by permissions of Princeton University Press. <https://trollopesociety.org/book/christmas-thompson-hall/>, gedownload 13 aug 2024. In Dutch translation, Trollope's Thompson Hall was published as a serial in a number of Dutch newspapers, e.g. Bataviaasch Handelsblad (first installment: 14 July 1883).

[One more literary version of the ink mistake motif appears in the novel (first published as a newspaper serial) *Goena Goena* (1887) by 'Maurits' (author and journalist P.A. Daum). In the following excerpt, ink is used by mistake instead of vinegar as a remedy against hysterics.]

Eerst toen ze thuiskwam en in haar kamer was, brak het los. Op gillende toon vertelde zij aan Lidia, hoe ze dáár was behandeld, en haar zuster, die het niet meer dan hoogst natuurlijk vond, begreep niets van deze ontroering en verontwaardiging, tot ze Betsy plotseling zich vast zag houden aan de tafel. Zij greep haar en liet haar neer op een bank; en daar ging het gillen voort, maar nu zonder woorden en afgebroken door een luide, lang aanhoudende lach, die, uit de zenuwwerking voortkomend, op anderer zenuwen werkte. Het was een consternatie, waarbij voor een ogenblik alle grieven en alle bedoelingen werden vergeten. Mevrouw Duhr, de zwager, Sarinah, - allen stormden de kamer binnen; Lidia riep om azijn; in een oogwenk kwam de bejaarde hospita, zelve in de hoogste mate zenuwachtig, met een fles van achteren; alle handen grepen ernaar, zonder verder te zien, vervuld met het idee, dat het goed was om iemand, die het op de zenuwen heeft, 't hoofd en de polsen met [p. 200] azijn nat te maken, en dat dit niet beter kon geschieden, dan door wat uit de fles te gieten. En terwijl allen zich beijverden, stroomde uit de azijnfles een zwarte gulp, die in vuile, dikke straaltjes over het gezicht en in de hals van Betsy liep.

'Schei uit! Het is inkt,' riep de man van Lidia met een vloek.

Iedereen schrikte ervan en was er verlegen mee. Mevrouw Duhr keek erg onthutst voor zich; de controleur had zich omgekeerd en proestte van het lachen.

'Ik kon het heus niet helpen,' stamelde de huisvrouw. 'De flessen zijn precies eender.'

Betsy gilte niet meer; het woord 'inkt' scheen meer kalmerend op haar zenuwen te hebben gewerkt, dan azijn bij mogelijkheid doen kon. Lidia, die het gesmoorde grinniken van haar man hoorde, moest zich geweld aandoen, en slikte telkens een opkomende lach weer in. Ze had onwillekeurig met haar zakdoek een veeg gegeven over 't gezicht van Betsy, toen ze het zwarte vocht zag, en dat had 't spektakel nog verergerd; Betsy zag er verschrikkelijk uit.

'Kom,' zei Lidia, ziende hoe goed in elk geval het middel had geholpen. 'Je moogt je wel gaan wassen. Mevrouw Duhr heeft bij vergissing...'

Zij kon niet verder, want Betsy had zich opgericht, en zag er nu met haar gezicht als een schoorsteenveger in functie, zó gek uit, dat het onmogelijk was voor Lidia haar sérieux te bewaren. Een ogenblik keek Betsy haar aan alsof ze niets begreep, daarop liep zij naar het toilet, keek in de spiegel en begon te huilen.

‘Wees niet kinderachtig,’ zei Lidia ruw, terwijl intussen haar lachlust door de tranen harer zuster bedaald was. ‘Wees niet kinderachtig; het is maar 'n beetje inkt; met water en zeep is het weer schoon, je bent waarachtig anders voor zo'n klein geruchtje niet vervaard!’

Maar het was gemakkelijker gezegd dan gedaan; het toeval scheen te willen, dat mevrouw Duhr een superieure kwaliteit inkt gebruikte, uiterst geschikt tot het merken van mensenhuiden, - althans ofschoon Betsy geweldig poetste hield zij over een deel van haar hals en haar gelaat een sterk uitgedrukte violetachtige tint, wat haar foecilelijk maakte en Lidia aanleiding gaf tot de openhartige [p. 201] verklaring: ‘Je ziet er wezenlijk niet kwaad uit in je gewone doen, maar er behoeft niet veel bij te komen om je 'n monster te maken.’

https://www.dbnl.org/tekst/daum001verz03_01/daum001verz03_01_0001.php

Only When She Got Home It all came out when she was finally home and in her room. In a shrill voice, Betsy recounted to Lydia how she had been treated there. Lydia, who found it all perfectly natural, couldn't understand Betsy's agitation and indignation—until she suddenly saw Betsy clinging to the table for support. Lydia grabbed her and eased her onto a bench, where Betsy continued shrieking, now without words, interrupted by a loud, long-lasting laugh. The laugh, stemming from nervous tension, began to affect everyone else's nerves. The scene caused such a commotion that, for a moment, all grievances and intentions were forgotten. Mrs. Duhr, the brother-in-law, Sarinah—everyone stormed into the room. Lydia called for vinegar. Within seconds, the elderly landlady appeared, highly flustered herself, carrying a bottle. Every hand reached for it in the shared belief that splashing vinegar on someone's head and wrists was the best remedy for nerves. Without further inspection, someone poured from the bottle. A black stream gushed out, running down Betsy's face and neck in thick, dirty streaks. “Stop! It's ink,” Lydia's husband shouted with a curse. Everyone froze, embarrassed and at a loss. Mrs. Duhr stared ahead, mortified; the inspector turned away, stifling his laughter. “I really couldn't help it,” stammered the landlady. “The bottles look exactly the same.” Betsy was no longer shrieking; the word ink seemed to have a more calming effect on her nerves than vinegar ever could. Lydia, hearing her husband's muffled chuckles, struggled to keep her composure, repeatedly suppressing her laughter. She instinctively wiped Betsy's face with her handkerchief when she saw the black liquid, but this only made things worse—Betsy looked utterly dreadful. “Come,” Lydia said, seeing how effective the “remedy” had been. “You should wash up. Mrs. Duhr made a mistake...” She couldn't finish because Betsy had stood up. With her face now resembling a chimney sweep's, she looked so ridiculous that Lydia could no longer keep a straight face. Betsy stared at her, confused, then went to the toilet, looked in the mirror, and began to cry. “Don't be childish,” Lydia said brusquely, her own laughter finally subdued by her sister's tears. “Don't be childish; it's just a bit of ink. With soap and water, it'll come off. Honestly, you're not usually the type to be rattled by such a small mishap!” But it was easier said than done. Fate seemed to have ensured that Mrs. Duhr used a particularly high-quality ink—perfect for marking skin. Despite Betsy's

vigorous scrubbing, parts of her neck and face retained a strong violet tint, making her look frightful. This prompted Lydia's candid remark: "You don't look bad under normal circumstances, but it doesn't take much to make you look monstrous."

Zaterdag 1 Januari 1938 — DE TELEGRAAF — Tweede Blad.

— Bengel, waarom geef je je zusje vloei-
papier te eten?
— Maar mammié, ze heeft een halve
flesch inkt opgedronken.

(Ric et Rac).

KUNSTAGENDA.

AMSTERDAM, 1 Januari.

De

- * **Hollandsche Schouwburg** (Bespreekno. 5155) 2 en 8.15 u.: Ballet Trudi Schoop „Alles is Liebe“.

Toon

- * **Carré** (Bespreekno. 53800), 2 en 8.15 u.: Internationaal Variété.
- * **Centraal Theater** (Bespreekno. 31814) 2.15 en 8.15 u.: Centraal Tooneel: Feestweek in Schouwburg.
- * **Grand Théâtre** (Bespreekno. 31814) 2.15 en 8 u.: Het Nieuwe Kluchtgezelschap: „60.000 p per maand“.
- * **Leidscheplein Theater** (Bespreekno. 35909) 8 u.: A.B.C.-Cabaret o.l.v. Louis Gimberg „Dok A.B.C.“ m.m.v. Corrie Vonk.
- * **Plantage Schouwburg** (Bespreekno. 53512) 8 u. Gez. Bouber: Betje regeert.
- * **Rika Hopper Theater** (Bespreekno. 51117) 2 Ned. Theater voor Kinderen: Popeye de zee-
* **Stadsschouwburg** (Bespreekno. 32932) 7.30 Amst. Tooneel Ver.: Gijsbrecht van Aemstel
De Brulloft van Kloris en Roosje.

Rev

De Telegraaf, 01-01-1938

De nieuwe Limburger, 12-10-1966

Appendix J: German Inky Night Cases

Ein probates Mittel Ein Gutsbesitzer in der Nähe von Landshut (Preußisch-Schlesien) bekam in einer der letzten Nächte so heftige Zahnschmerzen, daß er keinen Schlaf finden konnte. Infolge seines Jammerns wachte auch seine Gattin auf und riet ihm, die Backen mit sein auf den Fensterbrette stehenden Franzbrannt- wein einzureiben. Gesagt, geschehen, die Schmerzen hörten auf und der Mann schlief bald ein, nach- dem er sich gründlich eingerieben hatte. Als aber die Gattin am anderen Morgen nach dem Er- wachen einen Blick auf das Lager ihres Ehe- herrn geworfen hatte, erhob sie ein fürchtbares Angstgeschrei, denn an Stelle des Herren lag und schlief in dem Bette ein lebhafter Neger. Von dem Geschrei erwachte auch dieser bald und fragte unwirsch in guten schlesischen Deutsch, was denn eigentlich los wäre. Aus Rede und Gegenrede ergab sich endlich daß der Ahnungslose (es war der Ehemann) in der Nacht statt der Flasche mit Franzbranntwein die— Tintenflasche ergriffen hatte. Der Mann wie auch die Betten sahen schlimm aus. Die Tinte war »echt« und sehr schlecht ist sie abgegangen. Die bloße Ein- bildung hat zur Schmerzstillung beigetragen. *Znaimer Tagblatt* (Oostenrijk), 23 August 1902 Source: <https://anno.onb.ac.at/>

A Proven Remedy. A landowner near Landshut (Prussian Silesia) recently suffered such severe toothache during the night that he couldn't find any sleep. His groaning woke his wife, who advised him to rub his cheeks with the Franzbranntwein (rubbing alcohol) that was sitting on the windowsill. No sooner said than done—the pain stopped, and the man soon fell asleep after thoroughly applying it. However, the next morning, when the wife awoke and glanced at her husband's bed, she let out a terrible scream of fright. Instead of her husband, there was now a lively-looking "Negro" sleeping in the bed. The screaming woke the man, who grumbled in proper Silesian German, asking what on earth was going on. After some back-and-forth, it became clear that, during the night, the unsuspecting husband had grabbed the ink bottle instead of the Franzbranntwein. Both the man and the bed were in a terrible state. The ink was 'genuine' and very difficult to remove. It turned out that mere imagination had contributed significantly to easing the pain.

Eine lustige Geschichte. , Die »Passauer Zeitung« erzählt eine köstliche Geschichte, die auf voller Wahrheit beruht, und so recht den armseligen geistigen Zustand der Bevölkerung von Niederbayern, die bekanntlich durch und durch ultra-montan ist, charakterisirt: Vor einiger Zeit hatte sich in einer sehr dunklen Gegend des bayerischen Waldes eine seltsame Geschichte abgespielt, die in Folge neuerer Zwistigkeiten dabei betheiligter Individuen erst kürzlich ihrem ganzen Umfange nach in die Oeffentlichkeit drang. Einige übermüthige Bursche hatten sich nämlich mit einander verabredet, einen ebenso abergläubischen als geizigen Bauer und dessen ebenbürtige Eehälfte, die ihre alten Thaler fleißig nach Böhmen in die k. k. Lotterie trugen, einmal recht tüchtig zu foppen. Der in aller Stille entworfene Plan sollte im vorigen Advent zur Ausführung kommen. Wie gesagt, so gethan. In der Nacht vom 18. auf den 19. Dezember hörte der betreffende Bauer zwischen 11 und 12 Uhr ein ungewöhnliches Seufzen und Kettengerassel am Hofthore. Er stand auf, spritzte aus Furcht vor bösen Geistern eine Menge Weihwasser um sich und fragte, nachdem er sich noch mehrmals bekreuzt hatte, zum Fenster! hinaus: „Alle guten Geister loben Gott den Herrn, was ist dein Begehren?“ Wirklich vernahm er darauf eine geisterhafte Stimme, die ihm sagte, sie sei eine arme Seele aus dem Fegfeuer, die auf Erlösung warte. Nun war die Neugierde des Bauers schon geweckt. Er versicherte die arme Seele hoch und theuer, daß er alles thun wolle, um sie zu erlösen, sie möge nur anschaffen. Die geheimnißvolle Stimme dankte ihm für seine Freundlichkeit und sagte, sie werde in drei Tagen wieder kommen mit andern armen Seelen, und sie würden ihm dann, wenn er so und so viele Meffen lesen lasse und die anderen vorgeschriebenen Bedingungen erfüllen werde, aus Dankbarkeit vier Nummern sagen, die das nächstmal in der Lotterie kämen. Der Bauer solle aber vorläufig Niemandem etwas von dem, was er gehört und gesehen habe, erzählen. Der Bauer versprach Alles. Hierauf verschwand die arme Seele. Der Bauer schloß seinen Fensterladen, besprengte sich und seine liebenswürdige Eehälfte unter allerhand heiligen Sprüchen wieder recht tüchtig mit Weihwasser und legte sich zur Ruhe. Er vermochte aber nicht zu schlafen vor Freude über den in Aussicht stehenden Gewinn, und obwohl er Verschwiegenheit gelobt hatte, so konnte er doch nicht umhin, noch in derselben Nacht sein theures Weib von der gehabten Erscheinung in Kenntniß zu setzen und sie zu bestimmen, mit ausgestreckten Armen für die armen Seelen im Fegfeuer den vorgeschriebenen Rosenkranz mitzubeten. Endlich in der Nacht des dritten Tages nach dem ersten Erscheinen der armen Seele sollte die eigentliche Komödie vor sich gehen. Fast um dieselbe Zeit wie das erstemal, nämlich Nachts 11 Uhr, war ein Seufzen und Kettengerassel am Hofthore zu vernehmen. Der Bauer und seine liebende Gattin waren vor Gier nach dem Gelde selbigen Abend ohnehin nicht zu Bette gegangen und harrten mit Sehnsucht der Ankunft der armen Seelen. Nun war die verhängnißvolle Stunde gekommen. Das Seufzen und Kettengerassel wurde immer stärker. Plötzlich erschien eine feurige Gestalt am Fenster, so daß der Bauer und sein Weib erschrocken zurückfuhren und sich bekreuzten. Eine arme Seele, welche Feuer fraß, begann jetzt mit furchtbarer Stimme zu reden und fragte: „Seid ihr sündenrein? Wenn ihr das nicht seid, so könnt ihr uns nicht erlösen und werden euch die

versprochenen Lotterie-Nummern nicht mittheilen!" Der Bauer antwortete erschrocken: „Meine lieben armen Seelen, es ist schon ziemlich lange her, daß ich bricht hab' aber das Weib ist erst gegangen." Die arme Seele am Fenster erwiederte ernst: „Das hilft Alles nichts. Ihr müßt, um uns erlösen zu können, beide sündenrein sein, unschuldig wie ein neugebornes Kalb. Gebt Antwort: Wollt ihr einem Priester, der sich unter unS armen Seelen 'im Fegfeuer befindet, jetzt beichten oder nicht?" Der Bauer hatte anfangs nicht recht Lust, als aber die Gestalt am Fenster Miene machte, aus Nimmerwiederschen zu verschwinden, da verscheuchte der Gedanke an den Lotterie-Gewinn jedes Bedenken. Der Bauer beichtete. Als er aber zu Ende war, sagte die arme Seele, welche den Beichtvater spielte, mit drohender Geberde: „Bauer! Bauer! Du hast nicht Alles gesagt"— worauf der Bauer ängstlich erwiederte: „Ja verzeihn'S, es steht ja mein Weib hinter mir." Der Fegfeuer-Pfarrer ließ aber die Entschuldigung nicht gelten und die durch des Bauers Aeußerung ebenfalls neugierig gewordene Ehehälfte drang jetzt auch allen Ernstes in ihn, ja Alles zu beichten, da sonst er und das Geld ewig verloren wäre. Endlich nach langem Zögern gestand er unter Seufzen, daß er seinem Weibe mehrmals untreu geworden sei. Nun bedurfte es des ganzen Ernstes des Beichtvaters am Fenstert, um die wüthende Gattin zu besänftigen und erst das furchtbare Raffeln der Ketten am Hofthore und doS ferne Gebell des Höllenhundes, das sich vernehmen ließ, vermochte wieder Ruhe und Frieden zwischen den beiden Eheleuten herzustellen. Sodann kam die Reihe des BeichtenS an das Weib. Diese stand auS Rache sehr bereitwillig ein. daß sie ihrem Manne, diesem Schindteufel, wie sie ihn nannte, auch nicht immer die Treue gehalten hätte. Mann und Weib versöhnten sich hierauf auf das Zureden des eifrigen Seelsorgers auS dem Fegfeuer und harrten mit Ungeduld der Dinge, die da kommen sollten. Die Buße, die sie nun erhielten, bestand aus Rosenkränzen, Sankt Gregor-Meffen u. s. w. Auch mußten sie während des Erscheinens der Lotterie-Nummern, das jetzt erfolgen sollte, auf dem Boden knieend hochgeweihte schwarze Wetterkerzeln in der Hand halten und sollten sie nicht fallen lasten, bis Alles zu Ende wäre. Nach erfolgter Beichte, Buße, Belehrung und Lossprechung verschwand jetzt die Gestalt, das Seufzen und Kettengerassel am Hofthore dauerte aber immer noch fort. Nu» erschien die erste Nummer am Fenster. Sie war aber so schnell wieder fort, daß Bauer und Bäuerin darüber in Streit geriethen, welche Zahl es eigentlich war, und sie hätten sogar mit einander gerauft, wenn nicht furchtbares Kettengerassel und da-Erscheinen der zweiten Nummer sie zur Besinnung gebracht hätte. Sie versöhnten sich wieder und versprachen sich gegenseitig, von nun an besser aufzupassen. Die zweite Nummer blieb aber auffallend lange am Fenster, so daß beide sie deutlich am Fenster sehen konnten. Sodann erschien die dritte Nummer und blieb noch länger am Fenster. Die Bäuerin klagte bereits über den Schmerz, der ihr durch das schon ganz hinabgebrannte Wetterkerzeln bereitet wurde, allein der Bauer ermahnte sie mit guten und schlimmen Worten auszuharren im Leiden, indem er sie darauf hinwies, daß daS Feuer, welches die armen Seelen im Fegfeuer peinige, nach der Aussage des Herrn Pfarrers, noch viel ärger brenne, als ein Wetterkerzeln. Endlich kam die vierte Nummer. Kaum aber war diese am Fenster sichtbar, so ließ die Bäuerin und auch der Bauer, die sich schon arg die

Finger verbrannt hatten, die Kerzl fallen, worauf die Nummer sofort verschwand. Da erschien znm Schluß nochmals eine arme Seele am Fenster, ermahnte das fromme Ehepaar, die auferlegte Buße gewissenhaft zu verrichten und besprengte es noch mit Weihwasser, worauf der ganze Spuck ein Ende hatte. Bauer und Bäuerin beteten also gleich ihre Rosenkränze und plauderten die ganze Nacht mitsammen von dem Gelde, das sie bekämen, und berathschlagten, was sie Alles damit thun wollten. Als es Tag geworden war, wunderten sie sich, daß ihre Gesichter so schwarz seien. Sie merkten aber noch nicht, daß es gewöhnliche Tinte war, mit der sie ihr Beichtvater aus dem Fenster besprengt hatte, sondern meinten vielmehr in ihrem Wahne, sie wären nur durch die Berührung mit den armen Seelen schwarz geworden. Erst als sie wahrnahmen, daß die armen Seelen auch über ihr geselchtes Fleisch gekommen waren, gingen ihnen die Augen auf und sie erkannten, daß sie gefoppt waren. Von den erschienenen Nummern aber kam keine und auch von den armen Seelen ließ sich keine mehr sehen.— Es lebe die Dummheit!

Salzburger Volksblatt: unabh. Tageszeitung f. Stadt u. Land Salzburg, 18 September 1873

Source: <https://anno.onb.ac.at/>

A Hilarious Tale The Passauer Zeitung recounts a delightful story, purportedly true, that highlights the superstitious and credulous mindset of the population in Lower Bavaria, known for its ultramontane tendencies. Some time ago, in a remote part of the Bavarian Forest, a curious event took place. Due to recent disputes among the participants, the full extent of the story only recently became public. A few mischievous young men conspired to play a prank on a particularly superstitious and miserly farmer and his equally thrifty wife, who regularly carried their old coins to Bohemia to gamble in the imperial lottery. Their plan, concocted in secret, was to unfold during the previous Advent season. On the night of December 18th to 19th, the farmer heard eerie sighs and the clattering of chains near his farmhouse gate between 11 p.m. and midnight. Startled, he got up, sprinkled holy water liberally around him to ward off evil spirits, and—after crossing himself repeatedly—called out the window: ‘All good spirits praise the Lord our God. What do you want?’ A ghostly voice answered, claiming to be a poor soul from purgatory seeking deliverance. The farmer, now thoroughly intrigued, assured the poor soul that he would do whatever was necessary to help. The voice thanked him for his kindness and promised to return in three days, accompanied by other poor souls, to reveal four lottery numbers in gratitude—provided he would arrange for a specific number of masses and meet other prescribed conditions. The farmer was also warned not to speak of the event to anyone. He promised to keep silent. The ghost vanished, and the farmer shut his window, sprinkled himself and his wife generously with holy water while muttering sacred prayers, and went to bed. Overcome with joy at the prospect of winning the lottery, he couldn’t sleep. Despite his vow of silence, he couldn’t resist sharing the apparition with his wife that very night, even convincing her to pray the prescribed rosary for the poor souls in purgatory. *The Big Night.* On the third night, just before midnight, the promised drama unfolded. Once again, sighs and the clatter of chains echoed from the gate. The farmer and his wife, too eager to sleep, were already waiting anxiously. As the ghostly noises intensified, a fiery figure appeared at the window, terrifying the couple into crossing

themselves repeatedly. The fiery soul declared, 'Are you free of sin? If not, you cannot deliver us, nor will you receive the lottery numbers.' Frightened, the farmer admitted, 'It has been a long time since I confessed, but my wife went recently.' The fiery figure replied sternly, 'That is not enough. Both of you must be as sinless as a newborn calf. Do you wish to confess now to a priest among us poor souls in purgatory?' Though hesitant at first, the farmer reluctantly confessed, motivated by the thought of winning. After his confession, the fiery priest accused him of withholding something. Under pressure from both the priest and his wife, he admitted, with much anguish, that he had been unfaithful to her multiple times. The priest managed to calm the furious wife, assisted by ominous chain rattling and the barking of a spectral hellhound. When it was the wife's turn, she confessed readily out of spite, admitting she too had been unfaithful. The ghostly priest reconciled the couple and prescribed penance: rosaries, St. Gregory masses, and the lighting of sacred black candles during the lottery number revelation. The Lottery Numbers. As the couple knelt on the floor with burning candles in hand, the first number briefly appeared at the window. It vanished so quickly that they argued over what it had been, nearly coming to blows before the second number appeared. This one lingered long enough for them to see clearly. The third stayed even longer, but by the time the fourth appeared, their fingers were badly burned, and they dropped their candles. The final number vanished immediately. A ghostly figure reappeared, admonished them to complete their penance, and sprinkled them with "holy water" before disappearing. Overjoyed, the couple spent the night planning how to spend their winnings. The Revelation In the morning, they were surprised to find their faces blackened. Believing this to be a mark left by contact with the poor souls, they only realized the truth when they discovered the 'holy water' was ordinary ink. The numbers, of course, didn't win, and the poor souls never returned. The pranksters' elaborate joke had succeeded magnificently. Long live human folly!

Appendix K: Polish Inky Night Cases

With thanks to Filip Graliński

— **Kolor ich zdradził.** Jeden z drugorzędnych hoteli w dzielnicy nalewkowskiej, stał się niedawno widownią arcy zabawnego i drastycznej wielce natury wypadku.

Starym gościem hotelu był między innymi powien kupiec starozakonny z

miasta L., człowiek ze sfery zacofanej, ale wielce postyczuzy w stosunkach do plei pięknej.

Stołując się w restauracji hotelowej, zauważył w kuchni nie w kwiecie wieku już będącą mistrzynią garnków, nieestetycznej wprawdzie powierzchowności, lecz za to hojnie przez naturę obdarzoną objętością, do której zapalał niezmiernym afektem.

— Gorący adonis zdołał na prędko i dyskretnie zawiązać bliższą znajomość ze swym ideałem, który tegoż jeszcze dnia złożył mu wieczorem wizytę.

Zatłuszczona toaleta kucharki po niedawno co opuszczonych zajęciach kuchennych nie była zbyt pociągająca, więc adonis uznał za właściwe oblać ją wodą kolońską, z jednej ze stojących na oknie flaszeczek. Przedwstępna ta operacja, którą dokonał również na sobie kupiec, została przyjętą z obustronnem zadowoleniem.

Kucharka niebawem zeszła na powrót do kuchni. Tu sypnęły się zowząd jej pytania:

— Kto ci zawałał całą suknię i twarz atramentem? Co to ma znaczyć?

— Albo ja wiem! — odpowiada zakłopotana i zaambarasowana kucharka.

Niebawem zjawia się też na kolację ów kupiec, również od stóp do głów zaplamiony atramentem. To jeszcze bardziej pogorszyło położenie. Jednocześnie prawie wpada do restauracji posługacz hotelowy z krzykiem, iż znajdując drzwi od numeru zajętego przez owego kupca, otwarte, wszedł ze świecą aby się przekonać kto tam jest, znalazł wszystkie rzeczy tam w numerze jak to: meble, pościel i t. p. oblane atramentem.

— Tableau!...

Pokazało się, że nieostrożny kupiec przez pomyłkę w ciemności, wziął flaszkę z atramentem zamiast z wodą kolońską.

Kolor ich zdradził. Jeden z drugorzędnych hoteli w dzielnicy nalewzkowskiej, stał się niedawno widownią arcy zabawnego i drastycznej wiele natury wypadku. Stałym gościem hotelu był między innymi pewien kupiec starozakonny z miasta L., człowiek ze sfery zacofanej, ale wiele poetyczny w stosunkach do płci pięknej.

Stołując się w restauracji hotelowej, zauważył w kuchni nie w kwiecie wieku już będącą mistrzynię garnków, nieestetyczną w prawdzie powierzchowności, lecz za to hojną przez naturę obdarzoną objętością, do której zapalał niezmiernym afektem.

Gorący adonis zdołał na prędcie i dyskretnie zawiązać bliższą znajomość ze swym ideałem, który tegoż jeszcze dnia złożył na wieczorem wizytę.

Zatłuszczona toaleta kucharki po niedawno co opuszczonych zajęciach kuchennych nie była zbyt pociągająca, więc adonis uznał za właściwe oblać ją wodą kolońską, z jednej ze stojących na oknie flaszeczek. Przedwstępna ta operacja, którą dokonał również na sobie kupiec, została przyjęta z oburzonem zadowoleniem.

Kucharka niebawem zeszła na powrót do kuchni. Tłumy pękły się zewsząd i pytania:

Kto ci zalewał całą suknię i twarz atramentem? Co to ma znaczyć?

Albo ja wiem! – odpowiada zakłopotana i zaambarasowana kucharka.

Niebawem zjawila się też na kolację ów kupiec, również od stóp do głów zalany atramentem. To jeszcze bardziej pogorszyło położenie. Jednocześnie prawie wpada do restauracji obsługacz hotelowy z krzykiem, iż zajmując drzwi od numeru zajętego przez owego kapa, otwarte, wszedł ze świecą, aby się przekonać kto tam jest, znalazł wszystkie rzeczy tam w numerze tak brudne, jak... ściany i p. oblانة atramentem.

Tableau!..

Pokazało się, że nieostrożny kupiec przez pomyłkę w ciemności, wziął flaszkę z atramentem zamiast z wodą kolońską

‘Kolor ich zdradził’, *Kurier Poranny* (25 Jul 1887), 2

Their color betrayed them. One of the second-rate hotels in the Nalewki district recently became the scene of an extremely amusing and rather dramatic incident. Among the regular guests of the hotel was a certain Jewish merchant from the city of L., a man from a backward circle, but very poetic in his relations with the fairer sex. While dining in the hotel restaurant, he noticed in the kitchen a woman no longer in the bloom of youth, a master of pots and pans. Though her appearance was far from aesthetic, she had been generously endowed by nature with a certain fullness, to which he became immensely attracted. The passionate Adonis quickly and discreetly managed to strike up a closer acquaintance with his ideal, whom he visited later that same evening. The cook's greasy attire, fresh from her recent kitchen duties, was not particularly enticing. Therefore, Adonis deemed it appropriate to douse her with cologne from one of the bottles standing on the window. This preliminary operation, which the merchant also performed on himself, was met with indignant satisfaction. The cook soon returned to the kitchen. Crowds gathered, asking: Who doused your entire dress and face with ink? What does this mean? How should I know! — replied the embarrassed and confused cook. Soon after, the merchant also appeared for dinner, covered from head to toe in ink. This only worsened the situation. Almost simultaneously, a hotel attendant burst into the restaurant, shouting that, upon entering the room occupied by the same merchant with a candle in hand to check who was inside, he found everything in the room so dirty, like the walls and everything else, covered in ink. 'Table!' It turned out that the careless merchant, by mistake in the dark, took a bottle of ink instead of cologne.

Bibliography

- A baby...?' *The American Republican [West Chester Pennsylvania]*, 1 Apr 1873, 1.
- A Camp Meeting Difficulty.' *Shelby County Herald [Shelbyville MO]*, 22 Sep. 1880, 3.
- A Camp-Meeting Anecdote.' *The Troy Messenger [AL]*, 17 Mar 1881, 7.
- A Cholera Incident.' *Richmond Dispatch*, 4 Sep, 1873, 4.
- A Mt. Morris girl...?' *Sterling Standard*, 21 Nov, 1872, 1.
- A Slight Mistake.' *Weekly Dispatch*, 15 Sep 1901, 20.
- A Young Lady's Unpleasant Experience.' *Sheffield Weekly Telegraph*, 26 Dec 1908, 9.
- An absent-minded Congressman...?', *The Cincinnati Enquirer* (29 Jan 1881), 12
- Annual Meeting of the National Anti-Vivisection Society.' *Zoophilist*, 19 (1899), 45-52.
- Arnold. George *Parlor Theatricals: Or Winter Evenings' Entertainment*. New York: Dick and Fitzgerald, 1859.
- Brooks, Howard 'A Joke on Grandpa', *Palladium-Item* (27 Aug 1921), 13
- Chatterbox', *The Manhattan Mercury* (8 Oct 1938), 2
- Clara Morris...?' *Times Herald*, 11 Jan 1903, 35.
- Cured by Faith.' *Cornishman*, 28 Aug 1902, 7.
- Current Notes', *Knoxville Weekly Chronicle* (3 Aug 1870), 7
- Cut and Come Again.' *The Cincinnati Enquirer*, 12 Aug 1883, 13.
- Hughs, Ina 'Jane: She's Life's Best Banana Peel', *The Charlotte Observer* (17 Feb 1978), 28
- Lightning Plays.' *Million*, 17 Sep 1892, 7.
- Mildred.' *Daily Gazette for Middlesbrough*, 7 Jun 1895, 4.
- Mind Cure.' *Good Health* 27 (1892), 150-151.
- Modern Instance of Black Art.' *Davenport Sunday Democrat [Iowa]*, 25 Feb. 1894, 3.
- Mrs Carroll Channer...?' *Monroe Booster*, 1 May 1957, 4.

One night...’ *Fifeshire Advertiser*, 21 May 1881, 6.

Pastor Jacob Primmer at Kircaldy Battery.’ *Fife Free Press*, 5 Aug 1899, 2.

Railway Yarns II.’ *Civil & Military Gazette*, 3 May 1902, 5.

Remedy.’ *The Akron Beacon Journal*, 16 Jun 1940, 86.

Rochleau, Veronica ‘A Startling Mistake’, *Norwich Bulletin* (22 Aug 1912), 4

Ruffini, Giovanni *A Quiet Nook in the Jura*. Edinburgh: Edmonston and Douglas, 1867.

Sydney Smith’s Last Joke.’ *Morning Press*, 10 Apr 1874, 2.

Talk of the Town.’ *Chadron Record [Nebraska]*, 7 Jun 1895, 4.

The August issue of Ladies Home Journal...’ *Quad-City Times*, 23 Jul 1973, 8.

The friends of a Chicago man...’ *Sun Journal*, 6 Jun 1899, 4.

The Latest Yarn from America.’ *Portsmouth Evening News*, November 20, 1879, 3.

Turned Black in the Night.’ *Coventry Times*, 31 Aug 1892, 5.

What We heard [sic] and Saw within the Week.’ *The Jeffersonian*, May 28, 1874, 2.